

Studying the Multiobjective Variable Neighbourhood Search Algorithm when Solving the Relay Node Placement Problem in Wireless Sensor Networks

Jose M. Lanza-Gutierrez · Juan A. Gomez-Pulido

Received: date / Accepted: date

Abstract Nowadays, Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) are considered in many fields of application. In this paper, we study how to efficiently deploy relay nodes into previously-established static WSNs, with the purpose of optimising two relevant factors for the industry: average energy consumption of the sensors and average sensitivity area provided by the network. This is the so-called Relay Node Placement Problem (RNPP), which is a known NP-hard optimisation problem in the literature. With the purpose of tackling this MultiObjective (MO) optimisation problem, we consider two different approaches of the trajectory algorithm MO-VNS, assuming a wide range of stop conditions. Two additional standard genetic algorithms are included in this study, NSGA-II and SPEA2, which belong to evolutionary algorithms. The aim is to analyse the behaviour of MO-VNS comparing to traditional methodologies. To this end, the four metaheuristics are applied to solve a freely available data set. The results obtained are analysed following a widely accepted statistical methodology and considering three MO quality metrics: hypervolume, set coverage, and attainment surface. After studying the results, we conclude that MO-VNS provides better performance than the standard algorithms NSGA-II and SPEA2. Moreover, we verify that the addition of relay nodes is a good way to optimise traditional WSNs.

Keywords coverage · energy efficiency · metaheuristic · multiobjective optimization · relay node · wireless sensor network

1 Introduction

Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) have attracted unprecedented attention in the last years. This is evidenced by the high number of applications, which we find in the literature. For example, for environmental control, forest fire detection, industrial process monitoring, home automation, robotics, and intensive agriculture (Mukherjee and Ghosal (2008)).

A Traditional WSN (T-WSN) is composed of a set of sensors capturing information and a collector node, also called sink node, collecting all this data. There are some factors, which encourage the use of this technology, e.g. the sensors are small, low-cost, wireless, power-autonomous, and able to capture different types of measures in a same device. These features, among others, allow considering WSNs in environments, where the deployment of other technologies would be impossible or very expensive (Akyildiz et al (2002)).

Nevertheless, WSNs have also shortcomings, affecting important features, such as energy cost and Quality of Service (QoS). Traditionally, the sensors are powered by batteries to assume cheap devices and to avoid the use of wires. This means that WSNs are particularly sensitive to energy consumption, which directly affects the network QoS. The sensors send all the information captured to the collector node, involving an energy cost. If a star topology is considered, all the sensors are subject to a similar workload. However, if we assume a multi-hop topology, where the sensors relay data, the energy distribution could be unbalanced. This situation

Jose M. Lanza-Gutierrez · Juan A. Gomez-Pulido
Department of Technologies of Computers and Communications, University of Extremadura, Polytechnic School, Campus Universitario s/n, 10003 Caceres (Spain)
E-mail: jmlanza@unex.es

Juan A. Gomez-Pulido
E-mail: jangomez@unex.es

involves the existence of bottlenecks: sensors which are subject to higher energy cost than others.

With the aim of avoiding these bottlenecks, a new device specialised in communication tasks was added to T-WSNs: namely router or relay node (Hou et al (2005)). This device forwards all the information received to the collector node, having higher energy capacity than the sensors. The addition of relay nodes increases the network cost. Hence, it is important to carefully study, where these devices must be placed.

The design of a T-WSN depends on many factors, even more if we include routers. This way, Cheng et al (2003) and Chang and Tassiulas (2004) defined this issue as an NP-hard optimisation problem (Garey and Johnson (1979)). This type of problem cannot be tracked through traditional techniques, because of the high computing power needed. Instead, non-conventional methods are often considered, such as heuristics and Evolutionary Computation (EC, Zitzler (1999)).

In this paper, we study how to deploy relay nodes into previously-established static T-WSNs, with the objective of optimising some relevant factors. This is the so-called Relay Node Placement Problem (RNPP). To this end, we consider metaheuristics, which are techniques for solving very general types of problems. We provide the following contributions:

- We consider a MultiObjective (MO) approach of the RNPP. This way, two relevant factors for the industry are optimised: average energy cost of the sensors and average sensitivity area provided by the WSN.
- We assume two different approaches of the novel MultiObjective Variable Neighbourhood Search algorithm (MO-VNS), which is a trajectory algorithm proposed by Geiger (2008). Moreover, we include two additional standard algorithms SPEA2 (Zitzler et al (2001)) and NSGA-II (Deb et al (2000)), which belong to EC, for comparison purposes.
- These metaheuristics are applied to solve the freely available data set proposed by Lanza-Gutierrez and Gomez-Pulido (2011). Most papers in the literature assume non-public or randomly generated testbeds. Thus, this work could be replicated and enhanced by other authors in future works.
- The metaheuristics are compared assuming a widely accepted statistical methodology. To this end, the results obtained are analysed through three MO quality metrics: hypervolume, set coverage, and attainment surface (Zitzler and Thiele (1999), Zitzler (1999), and Fonseca and Fleming (1996), respectively).
- We consider a wide range of stop conditions based on the number of evaluations to analyse the behaviour of the algorithms. Criteria based on the

number of evaluations are fairer than others, such as elapsed time, depending on the computer used.

- We discuss the advantages provided by the addition of routers. To this end, we study the percentage in which the fitness functions are modified, regarding the number of routers deployed.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Related work is discussed in Section 2. The WSN definition is detailed in Section 3. The optimisation problem is defined in Section 4. The metaheuristics considered are explained in Section 5. The experimental methodology assumed is discussed in Section 6. The results obtained appear in Section 7. Finally, the concluding remarks are given in the last section.

2 Related work

We find two main lines of research for WSNs in the literature. Authors studying how to optimise T-WSNs through deployment strategies, new routing protocols, and network scheduling, among others. And works optimising such networks by deploying routers. Table 1 shows a summary of the related work for clarifying.

Taking the first line and considering heuristics, we may cite some contributions. Cheng et al (2003) assigned different power transmission levels to the sensors to minimise the energy consumption. Chang and Tassiulas (2004) optimised the routing protocol to maximise the network lifetime. Cardei and Du (2005) split WSNs into disjoint sets of sensors, deciding which set had to be active to maximise the network lifetime. Zhang and Hou (2005) studied how to keep a minimum number of sensors in the active mode, in order to optimise both coverage and connectivity. Liu et al (2010) split WSNs in a similar way to Cardei and Du (2005); however, they maximised the network lifetime, maintaining connectivity and coverage. Mahboubi et al (2014) developed deployment strategies based on Voronoi polygons to increase coverage in mobile WSNs.

EC was also considered by some authors for the same purpose. Konstantinidis et al (2008) assumed a MultiObjective Evolutionary Algorithm based on Decomposition (MOEA/D), with the aim of maximising both network lifetime and coverage. Jia et al (2009a) optimised the coverage rate and the number of sensors chosen, by deciding which sensors had to be active; to this end, they considered an MO Genetic Algorithm (GA). Jia et al (2009b) assumed NSGA-II with the same purpose as Jia et al (2009a), but considering sensors with adjustable sensing radius. Hu et al (2010) maximised the network lifetime through a GA, splitting the WSNs in a similar way to Cardei and Du

Table 1: Summing up related work.

Paper	Solving methodology	Objectives	Network-type
Cheng et al (2003)	heuristic - assigning power transmission levels	energy cost	T-WSN
Chang and Tassiulas (2004)	heuristic - routing protocol	network lifetime	T-WSN
Cardei and Du (2005)	heuristic - scheduling	network lifetime	T-WSN
Zhang and Hou (2005)	heuristic - scheduling	coverage and connectivity	T-WSN
Liu et al (2010)	heuristic - scheduling	network lifetime maintaining connectivity and coverage	T-WSN
Mahboubi et al (2014)	heuristic - deployment by Voronoi Polygons	coverage	mobile T-WSN
Konstantinidis et al (2008)	MOEA/D - deployment	network lifetime and coverage	T-WSN
Jia et al (2009a)	MO-GA - scheduling	coverage and number of sensors in the active mode	T-WSN
Jia et al (2009b)	NSGA-II - scheduling	coverage and number of sensors in the active mode, assuming sensors with adjustable sensing radius	T-WSN
Hu et al (2010)	GA - scheduling	network lifetime	T-WSN
Konstantinidis and Yang (2011)	MOEA/D - deployment	network lifetime and coverage, ensuring connectivity	T-WSN
Le Berre et al (2011)	MOEAs - deployment	network lifetime, coverage, and financial cost	T-WSN
Martins et al (2011)	MO-hybrid algorithm - scheduling	network lifetime	T-WSN
Yoon and Kim (2013)	GA - deployment	coverage	T-WSN
Mini et al (2014)	heuristic deployment and EC scheduling	network lifetime	T-WSN
Hou et al (2005)	heuristic - RNPP	network lifetime and network geometric deficiencies	TT-WSN
Tang et al (2006)	heuristic - RNPP	connectivity and fault-tolerance	TT-WSN
Wang et al (2007)	heuristic - RNPP	network cost, preserving connectivity and network lifetime	TT-WSN
Lloyd and Xue (2007)	heuristic - RNPP	network lifetime, preserving connectivity	ST-WSN
Han et al (2010)	heuristic - RNPP	fault-tolerance	ST-WSN
Xu et al (2010)	heuristic - RNPP	network lifetime and connectivity	TT-WSN
Misra et al (2011)	heuristic - C-RNPP	connectivity	ST-WSN
Misra et al (2013)	heuristic - C-RNPP	connectivity and survivability	ST-WSN
Nigam and Agarwal (2014)	heuristic - C-RNPP	delay	ST-WSN
Zhao and Chen (2007)	particle swarm optimisation - RNPP	energy cost	ST-WSN
Perez et al (2011)	MOEA - C-RNPP	energy cost and number of routers	ST-WSN
Peiravi et al (2013)	MO-GA - RNPP	network lifetime for different delay values	TT-WSN

(2005). Konstantinidis and Yang (2011) improved Konstantinidis et al (2008) by ensuring a certain connectivity. Le Berre et al (2011) optimised lifetime, coverage, and financial cost by applying some MultiObjective Evolutionary Algorithms (MOEAs). Martins et al (2011) assumed an MO hybrid algorithm in order to maximise the network lifetime. Yoon and Kim (2013) assumed a GA to deploy the sensors by optimising the network coverage. Mini et al (2014) proposed a two-step algorithm to increase the network lifetime. Firstly, they deployed the sensors at optimal locations, such that the network lifetime was maximum. Secondly, they scheduled the network through a swarm intelligence algorithm to increase the network lifetime.

The deployment of T-WSNs including many sensors presents a common shortcoming: the number of relayed packets is really high. Being as the sensors are energy-limited, it is habitual to consider redundant sensors to enhance the performance of the network. This situation implies high maintenance and deployment costs. As a possible solution to this issue, the optimal addition of routers allows designing WSNs without considering redundant sensors. Taking this line, we find two different approaches: Single-Tiered and Two-Tiered WSNs, ST-WSNs and TT-WSNs, respectively. The first approach assumes that all the devices can communicate among them following a multi-hop routing protocol. The second one is a cluster based network, where the sensors send data to the cluster head (a relay node) in one hop; then, the cluster head forwards the information to the sink node, following a multi-hop routing protocol, which considers other cluster heads and the sink node.

Following the second line of research, some authors assumed heuristics. Hou et al (2005) deployed TT-WSNs, optimising the network lifetime and mitigating the network geometric deficiencies. Tang et al (2006) deployed the minimum number of routers in TT-WSNs to ensure connectivity and fault-tolerance; to this end, they considered two polynomial time approximation algorithms. Wang et al (2007) minimised the network cost in TT-WSNs with constraints on connectivity and lifetime, considering two different models: the relay nodes were not energy limited and all the nodes were energy limited. Lloyd and Xue (2007) maximised the network lifetime in ST-WSNs, while they preserved connectivity by following two approaches: between each pair of sensors there was a connecting path composed of routers and/or sensors, and on the other hand, the path was consisted solely of routers. Han et al (2010) provided fault-tolerance in ST-WSNs, considering sensors with different transmission radius. Xu et al (2010) analysed the impact of random device placement on lifetime and connectivity in TT-WSNs. Misra et al (2011) deployed a minimum number of routers to ensure connectivity in ST-WSNs, being the relay nodes constrained to be placed at a subset of candidate locations, the so-called Constrained RNPP (C-RNPP). Following this constrained approach, Misra et al (2013) deployed a minimum number of relay nodes to ensure survivability and connectivity in energy-harvesting ST-WSNs. Nigam and Agarwal (2014) developed a branch-and-cut algorithm to place the minimum number of routers in ST-WSNs, such that there was a prespecified delay bound between the sensors and the collector node.

EC was also considered for this purpose. Thus, Zhao and Chen (2007) assumed a particle swarm optimisation to minimise the energy cost in ST-WSNs. Perez et al (2011) applied an MOEA to optimise the energy efficiency and the number of routers considered in ST-WSNs, assuming the C-RNPP. Peiravi et al (2013) developed a MO-GA for clustering TT-WSNs, optimising the network lifetime for different delay values.

This paper focuses on the second line of research, differing from the papers described before in the following: i) we assume an unconstrained single-tiered approach of the RNPP. ST-WSNs are usually considered in small and medium size networks, where the devices are low-cost, e.g. in intensive agriculture as ur Rehman et al (2014) discussed. In this network model, the routers are similar to sensors, but they do not have circuits for capturing information, having greater energy capacity (additional batteries, energy-harvesting devices, etc.). The search space of this unconstrained version is greater than in the C-RNPP, because the routers can be placed in anywhere of the surface. ii) it is well-known that MO metaheuristics provide a trade-off between the conflicting objective functions. This is not the case for heuristics, which provide a unique solution. In this work, we consider metaheuristics to solve the problem, in order that the network designer has several possibilities to deploy the network. Many works assumed heuristics to optimise ST-WSNs (Lloyd and Xue (2007), Han et al (2010), Misra et al (2011), Misra et al (2013), Nigam and Agarwal (2014)). However, we find only some papers applying metaheuristics to this end (Zhao and Chen (2007) and Perez et al (2011)). Nevertheless, Zhao and Chen (2007) considered a single-objective approach, but ours is MO. Hence, our approach is more realistic. Perez et al (2011) assumed a MO C-RNPP, but our approach is unconstrained.

This approach is partially inspired by some very early papers. In Lanza-Gutierrez et al (2012) and Lanza-Gutierrez et al (2013b), we considered NSGA-II and SPEA2 to solve the RNPP for ST-WSNs. In this paper, we present an extended version of the proposal in Lanza-Gutierrez et al (2013a), where we assumed a unique version of MO-VNS. Now, we present a more complete work, considering two different approaches of MO-VNS, a bigger data set, a new problem definition, an illustrative example of the RNPP, a wide-range of stop conditions, and additional comparative studies. Including an analysis of the gain, which accrue from adding relay nodes to traditional WSNs and a comparison among the Pareto fronts obtained through attainment surface representation. This line of research was assumed taking an important limitation: we did not find any free-access data set fitting this problem defini-

tion. We proposed our own data set in Lanza-Gutierrez and Gomez-Pulido (2011) to solve this deficiency. This means that we cannot directly compare the results obtained to other author approaches. Instead, we analyse how the objective functions are modified, regarding the number of relay nodes deployed.

3 Wireless sensor network model

This section discusses the WSN model considered in the RNPP. Firstly, we detail the general assumptions of the model. Next, we tackle the most important issues: the energy expenditure of the sensors, the coverage provided by the WSN, and the network lifetime.

3.1 General assumptions of the network model

Assuming the notation described in Figure 1, we consider the following assumptions:

1. The WSN consists of three types of wireless static devices: a sink node, $\tilde{s}_s$ sensors, and $\tilde{s}_r$ relay nodes, which are placed on a 2-D surface of size $d_x \times d_y$. The sensors are the only devices powered by batteries. The remainders have an unlimited power supply.
2. The only connection point of the WSN to the outside is the collector node.
3. On a regular basis and simultaneously, the sensors capture information about the environment with a sensitivity radius r_s , starting at time $t = 1 \in \tau$. This data is immediately sent to the sink node.
4. The relay nodes only forward all the information received to the sink node.
5. Two devices can be linked if they are at a distance lower than r_c .
6. Initially, all the sensors have the same energy charge in their batteries. If a sensor is out of energy, it cannot be linked again.
7. All the devices consider the same routing protocol provided by Dijkstra's algorithm, for minimum path length among devices, from Cormen et al (2009).
8. We suppose both a perfect synchronisation among all the devices and a perfect medium access as defined by S-MAC protocol (Ye et al (2002)).

This focus is realistic in the context of studying the initial deployment of WSNs, where the sensors have new batteries. Assumptions 1, 7, and 8 could limit the applicability of the approach. However, regarding the use of static devices in assumption 1, there are many applications for WSNs, where it is habitual to assume static devices, e.g. in intensive agriculture. According to assumption 7, studying routing protocols is not the objective of this work, but analysing deployment strategies.

τ	set of time periods, $\tau = \{0, 1, 2, \dots\}$.	$S_s(t)$	set of sensor coordinates with an energy charge greater than 0 at time $t > 0 \in \tau$, $S_s(t) \subseteq \tilde{S}_s$.
d_x	width of the surface, $d_x > 0$.	$s_s(t)$	number of sensors with an energy charge greater than 0 at time $t > 0$. It is the cardinal of $S_s(t)$, $s_s(t) \leq \tilde{s}_s$.
d_y	height of the surface, $d_y > 0$.	$\tilde{S}_r$	set of router coordinates, $\forall r \in \tilde{S}_r$, $r = (x, y)$ where $x \in [0, d_x]$ and $y \in [0, d_y]$.
r_s	sensitivity radius, $r_s > 0$.	$\tilde{s}_r$	number of routers. It is the cardinal of $\tilde{S}_r$.
r_c	communication radius, $r_c > 0$.	$\tilde{D}_p(t)$	set of demand points at time $t > 0$, $\forall p \in \tilde{D}_p$, $p = (x, y)$ where $x \in [0, d_x]$ and $y \in [0, d_y]$.
k	information packet size in bits, $k > 0$.	$\tilde{d}_p(t)$	number of demand points. It is the cardinal of $\tilde{D}_p(t)$.
co_{th}	coverage threshold, $co_{th} \in [0, 1]$.	$z_{j,i}^c(t)$	variable assuming 1 if $i \in S_s(t)$ is in the minimum path between $j \in S_s(t)$ and the collector node at $t > 0$.
iec	initial energy charge, $iec > 0$.	$w_i^c(t)$	variable which provides the next device in the minimum path between $i \in S_s(t)$ and the collector node at $t > 0$, $w_i^c(t) \in \{S_s(t) \cup \tilde{S}_r\} + c - i$.
α	path loss exponent, $\alpha \in [2, 4]$.		
β	transmission quality parameter, $\beta > 0$.		
amp	energy cost per bit of the power amplifier, $amp > 0$.		
c	collector coordinates, $c = (x, y)$ where $x \in [0, d_x]$ and $y \in [0, d_y]$.		
$\tilde{S}_s$	set of initial sensor coordinates, $\forall i \in \tilde{S}_s$, $i = (x, y)$, where $x \in [0, d_x]$ and $y \in [0, d_y]$.		
$\tilde{s}_s$	number of initial sensors. It is the cardinal of $\tilde{S}_s$.		

Fig. 1: Notation considered to model the WSN definition.

There are many other works, which are only specialised in this issue (Sha et al (2013)). Hence, the routing protocol could be replaced by any of these in future works. Assumption 8 supposes an ideal wireless communication model. As explained below and with the purpose of alleviating such principle, we consider an energy model, including a basic but relevant packet loss mechanism.

3.2 Energy expenditure of the sensors

As explained before, the sensors are powered by batteries. With the purpose of simulating the energy consumption of such devices, we consider the energy model proposed by Konstantinidis et al (2008). Following this approach, the energy expenditure is only due to the most expensive task: the sending. Thus, receiving, processing, and sensing tasks are considered negligible.

According to this model, the number of information packets sent by a sensor $i \in S_s(t)$ at time $t > 0$ depends on the number of packets that the sensor relays, as well as the number of packets generated by the sensing task of the sensor. In that case, a sensor generates an information packet per time unit. That is,

$$P_i(t) = 1 + \sum_{j \in \{S_s(t) - i\}} z_{j,i}^c(t) \quad t > 0. \quad (1)$$

This way, the energy expenditure suffered by a sensor i at time $t > 0$ is given by

$$E_i(t) = P_i(t) \cdot amp \cdot k \cdot \|i - w_i^c(t)\|^\alpha \cdot \beta, \quad (2)$$

where $\|\cdot\|$ is the Euclidean distance between two devices. Note that this value is calculated assuming two parameters, α and β , which simulate extra cost due to packet loss. Thus, the residual energy of a sensor i at time t is denoted by

$$Re_i(t) = \begin{cases} Re_i(t-1) - E_i(t) & \text{if } t > 0 \\ iec & \text{if } t = 0 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

3.3 Sensitivity area provided by the WSN

There are two main ways to obtain the coverage value in the literature (Wang (2011)). On the one hand, some authors consider that a sensor covers a circumference of radius r_s and area $\pi \cdot r_s^2$. Hence, the coverage provided by the network at time $t > 0$ is the union of the $s_s(t)$ areas. On the other hand, other authors assume a set of binary demand points uniformly distributed on the surface, where a demand point equals 1 if there is any active sensor covering it. Thus, the global coverage is calculated attending the number of active demand points. Note that a sensor is active at time t if its residual energy is greater than 0 at such time.

Although the first approach is more accurate, we opted for the second method, because it is less hard to compute. Accordingly, the sensitivity area provided by a WSN at time $t > 0$ is given by

$$A(t) = \frac{\sum_{p \in \tilde{D}_p(t)} 1_{\{\|p-i\| < r_s\}}}{\tilde{d}_p(t)}, \quad (4)$$

where $1_{\{\cdot\}}$ is the indicator function equalling 1 if the argument is true and 0 otherwise, being i an active sensor at such time.

3.4 Network lifetime definition

The network lifetime is defined as the number of time units, over which a WSN is able to provide useful information about its environment. We find several criteria in the literature to check this requirement, such as assuming a coverage threshold (co_{th}). This way, if the sensitivity area provided by the WSN is lower than co_{th} , we affirm that the amount of information is not enough. That is,

$$lf = |\{t > 0 \in \tau / A(t) > co_{th}\}|, \quad (5)$$

where $|\cdot|$ is the cardinal of the set.

4 Definition of the optimisation problem

Let f_1 be the Average Energy Consumption (AEC) of the sensors over the network lifetime, that is

$$f_1 = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^{lf} \left(\sum_{i \in S_s(t)} \frac{E_i(t)}{s_s(t)} \right)}{lf}, \quad (6)$$

where lf and $E_i(t)$ are given by (5) and (2), respectively. And let f_2 be the Average Sensitivity Area (ASA) provided by the WSN over the network lifetime, that is

$$f_2 = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^{lf} A(t)}{lf}, \quad (7)$$

where $A(t)$ is given by (4). Thus, we define the RNPP as an NP-hard Multiobjective Optimisation Problem (MOP), where given a traditional WSN, i.e. a set of sensors $\tilde{s}_s$ and a sink node, the objective is to deploy a set of routers $\tilde{S}_r$ to

$$\min(f_1), \max(f_2), \quad (8)$$

subject to

$$\forall r \in \tilde{S}_r, r = (x, y) / x \in [0, d_x] \text{ and } y \in [0, d_y]. \quad (9)$$

An illustrative example of this optimisation problem will be discussed in Section 6.

5 Multiobjective metaheuristics

In this section, we detail the MO metaheuristics considered to solve the RNPP. As stated before, this is an NP-hard optimisation problem, hence the use of exact techniques requires exponential time. Instead, approximate techniques are often used, such as EC.

There is an important set of techniques in EC: the Evolutionary Algorithms (EAs). They are population-based algorithms, which assume mechanisms from Darwin's theory of evolution, such as crossover, mutation, and survival (Back (1996)). EAs follow a known scheme: initially, the algorithm starts from a population of random individuals, each individual being a possible solution to the optimisation problem (step 1). Next, the best solutions of the population are selected to be the parents of the next generation, resulting a new offspring population through reproduction operators, e.g. crossover and mutation (step 2). Then, only the strongest

Fig. 2: Definition of the chromosome structure.

individuals survive at the end of the generation, i.e. the best solutions (step 3). Finally, the algorithm returns to step 2. This loop ends when a stop condition is reached, such as a maximum number of generations.

We consider two standard Genetic Algorithms (GAs): NSGA-II and SPEA2. These algorithms belong to a subtype of EAs, which encode their individuals as chromosomes. In addition to EC, we assume a novel metaheuristic belonging to trajectory algorithms, which are characterised by following a trajectory in the search space. This algorithm is called MO-VNS and shows a good performance in many optimisation problems.

As stated before, GAs require a specific encoding. Hence, we defined a straightforward representation: a chromosome is composed of $\tilde{s}_r$ genes, where a gene is the 2D-coordinate of a router (see Fig. 2). The same encoding is considered for the three metaheuristics.

5.1 Non-dominated sorting genetic algorithm (NSGA-II)

This algorithm was proposed by Deb et al (2000) as an improved version of the previous NSGA. NSGA-II is characterised by using two populations of the same size PS , where at generation $t \in \mathbb{N}$, P_t saves the parents of such generation and Q_t is the offspring population generated through individuals in P_t . Another important feature is the use of two MO measures to guide the selection process: rank and crowding.

The rank is calculated by splitting the population into different fronts. Then, the solutions in the non-dominated front have rank 0, the solutions in the non-dominated front in the absence of the previous one have rank 1, etc. The authors propose a fast sorting method called *fast non-dominated sort* to this end. The crowding distance is a density measure, denoting how close an individual is to its neighbors in the same front. Based on these two metrics, the authors define an elitist crowded-comparison operator to guide the selection process.

Let a and b be two possible solutions to an optimisation problem. Then, if a_{rank} and b_{rank} are the rank of a and b , and if a_{crow} and b_{crow} are the crowding of a and b , the crowded-comparison operator $\prec_n$ is expressed as

$$a \prec_n b \quad \text{if} \left((a_{rank} < b_{rank}) \text{ or } \left((a_{rank} = b_{rank}) \text{ and } (a_{crow} > b_{crow}) \right) \right), \quad (10)$$

i.e. a is better than b if one of the conditions holds.

Algorithm 1 NSGA-II

Input: PS, mutP, and crossP
Output: A set of solutions to the optimisation problem

```

1:  $P_t \leftarrow \{ \}$  and  $Q_t \leftarrow \{ \}$ 
2: while  $|P_t| < PS$  do
3:    $P_t \leftarrow P_t \cup \text{generateRandomIndividual}()$ 
4: end while
5: while not stop condition do
6:    $R_t \leftarrow P_t \cup Q_t$   $\triangleright$  Combine both populations
7:    $Fr \leftarrow \text{fastNonDominatedSort}(R_t)$   $\triangleright Fr = \{Fr_1, Fr_2, \dots\}$ 
8:    $P_{t+1} \leftarrow \{ \}$  and  $i \leftarrow 1$ 
9:   while  $|P_{t+1}| + |Fr_i| \leq PS$  do
10:     $\text{crowdingAssignment}(Fr_i)$ 
11:     $P_{t+1} \leftarrow P_{t+1} \cup Fr_i$  and  $i \leftarrow i + 1$ 
12:   end while
13:   if  $|P_{t+1}| < PS$  then
14:      $\text{Sort}(Fr_i, \prec_n)$   $\triangleright$  Sort  $Fr_i$  by  $\prec_n$ 
15:      $P_{t+1} \leftarrow P_{t+1} \cup Fr_i[1 : (PS - |P_{t+1}|)]$ 
16:   end if
17:    $Q_{t+1} \leftarrow \text{generateOffspringPopulation}(P_{t+1}, \text{mutP}, \text{crossP})$ 
18:    $t \leftarrow t + 1$ 
19: end while

```

Algorithm 2 generateRandomIndividual()

Output: a random individual

```

1: for  $r = 1$  to  $s_r$  do
2:    $\text{individual}[r].x \leftarrow \text{random}(0, d_x)$ 
3:    $\text{individual}[r].y \leftarrow \text{random}(0, d_y)$ 
4: end for
5:  $\text{evaluateSolution}(\text{individual})$ 
6: return individual

```

As given in Algorithm 1, Q_t is initially empty and P_t is randomly generated (lines 1-4). At each iteration and so long as the stop criterion is not reached (line 5), both populations are combined into a new one called R_t of size $2PS$ (line 6). Next, R_t is sorted into non-dominated fronts (line 7). Then, the best PS solutions of R_t are inserted into a new P_{t+1} . To this end, full fronts are added to the new parent population in ascending order, i.e. from best to worst rank, until P_{t+1} is filled, or instead, the size of a front is greater than the remaining free space in P_{t+1} (lines 8-12). In such case, the front is sorted by $\prec_n$, and then, only its best $PS - |P_{t+1}|$ solutions are added to P_{t+1} (lines 13-16). Finally, a new offspring population is generated by individuals in P_{t+1} . To this end, so long as Q_{t+1} is not filled, two individuals from P_{t+1} are selected by binary tournament (Deb et al (2000)). Next, based on them, a new individual is generated and inserted into Q_{t+1} through crossover and mutation operators (line 17).

The generation of random individuals is detailed in Algorithm 2, where $\text{random}(a,b)$ $a, b \in \mathbb{R}$ is a function providing random numbers in the interval $[a,b]$.

The crossover operator is assumed to recombine two individuals, with the hope of making a better solution. There are many crossover operators in the literature, such as uniform crossover, cut and splice, and polynomial crossover, among others (Back (1996)). In this approach, we consider the standard one-point crossover. Thus, a gene of the chromosome is randomly selected as

Algorithm 3 Mutation operator

Input: individual and mutP
Output: a mutated individual

```

1:  $\text{prevIndividual} \leftarrow \text{individual}$   $\triangleright$  Backup
2: for  $r = 0 \rightarrow s_r$  do  $\triangleright$  Modify coordinates for each router
3:   if  $\text{random}(0,1) < \text{mutP}$  then
4:      $\text{individual}[r].x \leftarrow \text{random}(0, d_x)$ 
5:      $\text{individual}[r].y \leftarrow \text{random}(0, d_y)$ 
6:      $\text{evaluateSolution}(\text{individual})$ 
7:     if  $\text{prevIndividual} \succ \text{individual}$  then
8:        $\text{individual} \leftarrow \text{prevIndividual}$   $\triangleright$  Restore backup
9:     else
10:       $\text{prevIndividual} \leftarrow \text{individual}$   $\triangleright$  Accept changes
11:    end if
12:  end if
13: end for
14: return individual

```

crossover point. Then, routers from an individual of the pair are copied to the new individual up to this gene. Next, the remaining routers are copied from the another individual from that point. This operator depends on the crossover probability (crossP in Algorithm 1), determining if the recombination is performed. Otherwise, the best individual of the incoming pair is returned.

The mutation is used to increase the population diversity. This operator depends on the mutation probability (mutP in Algorithms 1 and 3). In our approach, this value is the probability that each gene of the chromosome is mutated. As described in Algorithm 3, we follow a greedy strategy: each time a gene is mutated (lines 4-5), the individual is evaluated (line 6), and then, if and only if the mutated individual is not dominated by the previous one, the change is accepted (lines 7-8). Otherwise, the gene takes the previous values (lines 9-10). In this pseudocode, the random function is the same as previously discussed for Algorithm 2.

5.2 Strength pareto evolutionary algorithm (SPEA2)

This algorithm was implemented by Zitzler et al (2001) as a revised version of the previous SPEA. SPEA2 considers two populations P_t and $\bar{P}_t$ of sizes PS and $\bar{P}S$, respectively. At generation $t \in \mathbb{N}$, P_t is a regular population, saving the individuals produced in such generation and $\bar{P}S$ is an auxiliary population, which has the best individuals generated until such time.

The selection process of the algorithm is based on the Pareto dominance concept and additional density measure as fine assignment. This way, each individual $a \in \{P_t \cup \bar{P}_t\}$ is assigned a strength value denoted by

$$S(a) = |\{b / b \in \{P_t \cup \bar{P}_t\} \wedge a \succ b\}|, \quad (11)$$

providing the number of solutions a dominates. On the basis of the strength values, the raw fitness of a is given

Algorithm 4 SPEA2

Input: PS, mutP, and crossP
Output: A set of solutions to the optimisation problem

- 1: $P_t \leftarrow \{ \}$ and $\bar{P}_t \leftarrow \{ \}$
- 2: **while** $|P_t| < PS$ **do**
- 3: $P_t \leftarrow P_t \cup \text{generateRandomIndividual}()$
- 4: **end while**
- 5: **while** not stop condition **do**
- 6: $F \leftarrow \text{fitnessAssignment}(P_t \cup \bar{P}_t)$ $\triangleright$ Get fitness values
- 7: $\bar{P}_{t+1} \leftarrow \text{environmentalSelection}(F)$ $\triangleright$ Update archive
- 8: $P_{t+1} \leftarrow \text{generateNewPopulation}(\bar{P}_{t+1}, \text{mutP}, \text{crossP})$
- 9: $t \leftarrow t + 1$
- 10: **end while**

by the strength of its dominators in $P_t \cup \bar{P}_t$, that is

$$R(a) = \sum_{b \in \{P_t \cup \bar{P}_t\}, b \succ a} S(b). \quad (12)$$

Thus, if a is assigned a raw fitness equaling 0, it denotes a non-dominated individual. On the other hand, a high raw fitness corresponds to a solution dominated by many individuals. When most individuals are non-dominated, the raw fitness is lacking. Hence, additional density information is added. This measure is based on the k -th nearest neighbor method. This way, given the individual a , the distance (in the objective space) to all other individuals in both populations are calculated and sorted in increasing order. Then, the k -th element of the list is taken, equaling k to $(PS + \bar{PS})^{1/2}$. Thus, the density information of a is given by

$$D(a) = \frac{1}{\sigma_a^k + 2}, \quad (13)$$

where σ_a^k is the k -th element. The combination of both measures yields a fitness value, which is used to guide the selection process of the algorithm. That is,

$$F(a) = R(a) + D(a). \quad (14)$$

As described in Algorithm 4, initially P_t is randomly generated (see Algorithm 2) and $\bar{P}_t$ empty (lines 1-4). At each generation and so long as the stop condition is not reached, fitness values of individuals in both populations are obtained considering (14) (line 6). Next, the archive is updated by adding solutions from $P_t \cup \bar{P}_t$ (line 7). Finally, a new P_{t+1} is generated by individuals in $\bar{P}_{t+1}$ (line 8). To this end, we consider the binary tournament and both mutation and crossover operators, as previously discussed for NSGA-II.

5.3 Multiobjective variable neighborhood search algorithm (MO-VNS)

The algorithm MO-VNS was proposed by Geiger (2008) as a MO version of the traditional VNS. As previously

Algorithm 5 MO-VNS

Input: $\tilde{n}_s$ and dv [and mutP if MO-VNS_PER]
Output: A set of solutions to the optimisation problem

- 1: $P_{v_t} \leftarrow \text{generateRandomIndividual}()$ and $S_{c_t} \leftarrow \{ \}$
- 2: $N_s \leftarrow \text{generateNeighborhoodStructures}(\tilde{n}_s, dv)$
- 3: **while** not stop condition **do**
- 4: **while** $P_{v_t} \neq S_{c_t}$ **do** $\triangleright$ There are solutions non-considered
- 5: $a \leftarrow \text{selectNonConsideredSolution}(P_{v_t}, S_{c_t})$
- 6: $k \leftarrow \text{selectNeighborhoodStructure}(N_s)$
- 7: **while** $k \leq \tilde{n}_s$ **do**
- 8: $\bar{a} \leftarrow \text{generateNeighborhoodSolution}(a, n_{s_k})$
- 9: $P_{v_t} \leftarrow P_{v_t} \cup \{ \bar{a} \}$ and $S_{c_t} \leftarrow S_{c_t} \cup \{ a \}$
- 10: $\text{update}(P_{v_t}, S_{c_t})$ $\triangleright$ Only non-dominated solutions
- 11: **if** $\bar{a} \in P_{v_t}$ **then**
- 12: $k \leftarrow k + 1$ and $a \leftarrow \bar{a}$
- 13: **else**
- 14: $k \leftarrow k + 1$
- 15: **end if**
- 16: **end while**
- 17: **end while**
- 18: **if** MO-VNS_PER **then**
- 19: $P_{v_{t+1}} \leftarrow \text{performPerturbation}(P_{v_t}, \text{mutP})$
- 20: **else**
- 21: $P_{v_{t+1}} \leftarrow P_{v_t}$
- 22: **end if**
- 23: $S_{c_{t+1}} \leftarrow \{ \}$ and $t \leftarrow t + 1$
- 24: **end while**

discussed, this metaheuristic belongs to trajectory algorithms. This type of algorithm starts from a random solution, which is improved over time, so long as a local optimum is found or a stop condition is reached. This way, at each iteration, a new candidate solution is generated in the neighborhood of the current solution. Then, the new solution replaces the previous one, only if an improvement is achieved. Otherwise, it is discarded.

MO-VNS does not exactly follow a trajectory in the objective space. Instead, the algorithm explores distant neighborhoods by a set of neighborhood structures called N_s . In this approach, we assume that a neighborhood structure is a value determining the maximum displacement from the initial coordinates, that the routers of a solution could experience during the local search. Thus, N_s is expressed as

$$N_s = \left\{ n_{s_k} \in \mathbb{R} / n_{s_k} = \frac{\min\{d_x, d_y\} * k}{dv * \tilde{n}_s} \right\}, \quad (15)$$

for $k = 1, 2, \dots, \tilde{n}_s$, where $n_{s_k} < n_{s_{k+1}}$, $\tilde{n}_s$ is the number of neighborhood structures, i.e. the cardinal of N_s , $\min\{d_x, d_y\}$ is the minimum value between d_x and d_y , and dv is a factor which delimits the displacement. Accordingly, if $k = \tilde{n}_s$ and $dv = i$, $i \in \mathbb{N}$, the maximum displacement is $\min\{d_x, d_y\}/i$.

MO-VNS assumes two populations P_{v_t} and S_{c_t} . At iteration $t \in \mathbb{N}$, P_{v_t} is a regular population, keeping only non-dominated solutions and S_{c_t} saves the solutions from P_{v_t} considered during the local search.

As described in Algorithm 5, a random solution is initially inserted into P_{v_t} (see Algorithm 2) and S_{c_t} is empty (line 1). At each iteration and so long as the stop condition is not reached, each individual in P_{v_t}

is selected to generate a new solution. Thus, a non-considered solution $a \in P_{v_t}$, $a \notin S_{c_t}$ and a neighborhood structure $n_{s_k} \in N_s$ are randomly selected (lines 5-6). Next, a new solution $\bar{a}$ is generated in the neighborhood of a through the expression given by

$$R_{\bar{a}_z} = R_{a_z} + \left(\frac{n_{s_k}}{2} - rand(n_{s_k}) \right) \quad n_{s_k} \in N_s, \quad (16)$$

for $z = 1, 2, \dots, \tilde{s}_r$, where $k = 1, 2, \dots, \tilde{n}_s$, $rand(n_{s_k})$ is a random number in the interval $[0, n_{s_k}]$, and R_{a_z} and $R_{\bar{a}_z}$ are the routers placed on the z -th gene of a and $\bar{a}$, respectively (line 8). Next, the new solution $\bar{a}$ is added to P_{v_t} and a is inserted into S_{c_t} (line 9). Then, P_{v_t} is updated, removing all the dominated solutions (line 10). Note that, if a solution from P_{v_t} is removed, it is also removed from S_{c_t} . If after this procedure, $\bar{a}$ is in P_{v_t} , the local search provided a good performance. Hence, the search is repeated again, taking $\bar{a}$ as base solution and considering $n_{s_{k=1}}$ (lines 11-12). Otherwise, k is increased so long as k equals $\tilde{n}_s$ (lines 13-14).

We consider two different approaches of MO-VNS: with and without perturbation mechanism, called MO-VNS and MO-VNS_PER, respectively (Geiger (2008)). The perturbation mechanism is performed once all the solutions in P_{v_t} are explored, i.e at the end of the iteration (see Algorithm 5, lines 18-19). The aim of this mechanism is to avoid local minima. With this purpose, we apply the mutation operator described in Algorithm 3 for each individual in P_{v_t} .

6 Solving strategy

In this section, we discuss some important details about the solving strategy. Firstly, we describe the data set considered. Next, the experimental methodology is presented. As the RNPP is a MOP, we discuss the MO metrics considered to analyse the results obtained. Finally, we detail the methodology followed to configure the algorithms before performing the experiments.

6.1 Data set considered

As stated before, we assume a freely available data set proposed by ourselves in Lanza-Gutierrez and Gomez-Pulido (2011), because standard test cases do not exist for the problem being studied. Thus, we provide a common framework for studying the RNPP, allowing comparing different solving strategies in a better way.

This data set is composed of four different scenarios, with sizes 50x50, 100x100, 200x200, and 300x300. A traditional WSN is deployed in each scenario, considering the minimum number of sensors to cover the

whole surface. Thus, if the area of the surface is $d_x \cdot d_y$ and a sensor covers a circumference of radius r_s , then the lower bound of the minimum number of sensors is

$$\tilde{s}_s = \left\lceil \frac{d_x \cdot d_y}{\pi \cdot r_s^2} \right\rceil. \quad (17)$$

The sensors are deployed considering a singleobjective GA, optimising the coverage provided by the WSN, being the sink node placed in the middle of the scenario. The sensors coordinates obtained are shown in Fig. 3.

As stated previously, this WSN model assumes several parameters. We consider $\alpha=2$, $\beta=1$, $co_{th}=70\%$, $k=128\text{KB}$, $r_s=15\text{m}$, and $amp = 100\text{pJ/bit/m}^2$, from Martins et al (2011) and Konstantinidis and Yang (2011). Two r_c values are assumed to represent WSNs with different communication capacities, 30 and 60m, respectively. Thus, two instances are defined for each scenario following the notation $d_x \times d_y - r_s - r_c$ (see Fig. 3).

Being as adding relay nodes increases the network cost, we do not include more than 20% of these devices regarding the number of sensors. The *test cases* field shows the number of routers, which we will add to optimise the network. This way, we define two test cases for the 50x50 scenario, six for the 100x100, ten for the 200x200, and twelve for the 300x300.

Figure 3 also shows the value of the fitness functions without considering routers ($\tilde{s}_r=0$). In addition, in Fig. 4, we study the energy distribution at the end of the network lifetime. Analysing these plots, we can check that the distribution is really unbalanced, and then, it is necessary to optimise such networks.

Based on this data set, we propose an illustrative example of the RNPP in Fig. 5. To this end, we consider the instance 100x100_15_60, in which we deploy a router in the position (20,20). In this figure, we show the evolution of the energy charge of the sensors over time, as well as the fitness functions, and the sensitivity area. Note that when $A(t)$ is lower than co_{th} , the network lifetime is ended. Analysing the 3D-plot of the energy distribution, we reach that the energy cost of the sensors in the surrounding of the router is lower than the one shown in Fig. 4, without considering routers. Hence, the addition of relay nodes really affects the distribution of the energy expenditure in the network.

6.2 Experimental methodology

The data set is tackled by considering the metaheuristics previously discussed. To this end, we perform 31 independent runs for each test case and algorithm. 30 runs is a quite typical value to reach statistical validity, from Hays and Winkler (1970). As stop condition and

Instance name ($d_x \times d_y, r_s, r_c$)	Fitness values $\bar{s}_r = 0$		Test cases ($\bar{s}_r$)
	f_1	f_2	
50x50_15_30	0.035	91.75%	1
50x50_15_60	0.035	91.75%	1

Instance name ($d_x \times d_y, r_s, r_c$)	Fitness values $\bar{s}_r = 0$		Test cases ($\bar{s}_r$)
	f_1	f_2	
100x100_15_30	0.1091	89.24%	1, 2, 3
100x100_15_60	0.1482	86.63%	1, 2, 3

Instance name ($d_x \times d_y, r_s, r_c$)	Fitness values $\bar{s}_r = 0$		Test cases ($\bar{s}_r$)
	f_1	f_2	
200x200_15_30	0.2791	87.10%	1, 2, 4, 6, 9
200x200_15_60	0.3871	82.43%	1, 2, 4, 6, 9

Instance name ($d_x \times d_y, r_s, r_c$)	Fitness values $\bar{s}_r = 0$		Test cases ($\bar{s}_r$)
	f_1	f_2	
300x300_15_30	0.4225	76.44%	2, 4, 6, 12, 18, 24
300x300_15_60	0.6295	81.22%	2, 4, 6, 12, 18, 24

$(\bar{S}_s)$ Sensor coordinates: sensorID , (x-coordinate, y-coordinate)											
#1	(8,34)										
#2	(37,38)										
#3	(36,9)										
#4	(14,12)										

$(\bar{S}_s)$ Sensor coordinates: sensorID , (x-coordinate, y-coordinate)											
#1	(17,10)	#5	(76,13)	#9	(13,34)	#13	(85,87)				
#2	(63,66)	#6	(59,90)	#10	(13,88)	#14	(38,55)				
#3	(88,59)	#7	(65,40)	#11	(40,30)	#15	(13,59)				
#4	(38,84)	#8	(89,35)	#12	(47,10)						

$(\bar{S}_s)$ Sensor coordinates: sensorID , (x-coordinate, y-coordinate)											
#1	(87,14)	#10	(131,139)	#19	(155,189)	#28	(111,162)	#37	(167,13)	#46	(35,153)
#2	(185,187)	#11	(26,120)	#20	(96,187)	#29	(13,167)	#38	(12,13)	#47	(70,39)
#3	(161,92)	#12	(188,159)	#21	(135,80)	#30	(41,182)	#39	(157,39)	#48	(185,75)
#4	(158,143)	#13	(83,62)	#22	(161,118)	#31	(144,113)	#40	(41,41)	#49	(129,38)
#5	(61,13)	#14	(158,65)	#23	(69,86)	#32	(29,67)	#41	(139,164)	#50	(37,14)
#6	(62,112)	#15	(103,78)	#24	(80,134)	#33	(106,128)	#42	(121,59)	#51	(9,68)
#7	(165,167)	#16	(185,132)	#25	(55,64)	#34	(10,140)	#43	(117,101)	#52	(186,46)
#8	(100,38)	#17	(86,161)	#26	(41,94)	#35	(189,116)	#44	(136,112)	#53	(14,189)
#9	(14,41)	#18	(52,132)	#27	(89,104)	#36	(61,158)	#45	(125,188)	#54	(69,186)

$(\bar{S}_s)$ Sensor coordinates: sensorID , (x-coordinate, y-coordinate)											
#1	(131,223)	#20	(97,39)	#39	(9,185)	#58	(124,34)	#77	(288,121)	#96	(290,95)
#2	(64,71)	#21	(289,254)	#40	(239,103)	#59	(112,108)	#78	(138,194)	#97	(40,40)
#3	(37,255)	#22	(285,30)	#41	(231,132)	#60	(100,157)	#79	(41,151)	#98	(286,150)
#4	(126,57)	#23	(173,264)	#42	(12,261)	#61	(41,285)	#80	(285,197)	#99	(112,201)
#5	(254,288)	#24	(111,82)	#43	(197,247)	#62	(91,61)	#81	(246,75)	#100	(251,13)
#6	(13,234)	#25	(147,136)	#44	(169,12)	#63	(197,61)	#82	(164,69)	#101	(69,290)
#7	(190,86)	#26	(167,288)	#45	(195,286)	#64	(63,132)	#83	(163,156)	#102	(14,136)
#8	(261,46)	#27	(225,287)	#46	(266,262)	#65	(185,178)	#84	(260,212)	#103	(58,176)
#9	(147,15)	#28	(149,247)	#47	(86,113)	#66	(56,204)	#85	(39,93)	#104	(91,250)
#10	(13,10)	#29	(102,224)	#48	(90,12)	#67	(263,107)	#86	(119,11)	#105	(203,221)
#11	(144,275)	#30	(63,241)	#49	(175,235)	#68	(93,281)	#87	(226,55)	#106	(39,226)
#12	(64,14)	#31	(286,58)	#50	(65,265)	#69	(218,157)	#88	(121,243)	#107	(72,153)
#13	(208,35)	#32	(278,12)	#51	(240,262)	#70	(121,138)	#89	(278,171)	#108	(61,103)
#14	(193,14)	#33	(219,81)	#52	(173,129)	#71	(179,39)	#90	(119,290)	#109	(16,208)
#15	(39,14)	#34	(221,10)	#53	(86,178)	#72	(74,226)	#91	(12,59)	#110	(13,87)
#16	(117,264)	#35	(260,135)	#54	(13,287)	#73	(85,200)	#92	(68,42)	#111	(285,226)
#17	(186,110)	#36	(138,164)	#55	(85,88)	#74	(14,32)	#93	(181,206)	#112	(212,107)
#18	(138,83)	#37	(207,193)	#56	(93,134)	#75	(268,79)	#94	(155,216)	#113	(212,264)
#19	(253,236)	#38	(13,161)	#57	(13,110)	#76	(256,188)	#95	(225,238)	#114	(202,132)

Fig. 3: Description of the data set considered in this work.

Fig. 4: Analysis of the energy consumption at the end of the network lifetime ($\bar{s}_r = 0$).

with the objective of studying the behaviour of the algorithms in depth, we assume a wide range of criteria based on the number of evaluations: 25 000, 50 000, 100 000, 200 000, 300 000, 400 000, 500 000, 600 000, 700 000, and 800 000 evaluations.

6.3 Multiobjective quality metrics

If a single objective optimisation problem is considered, comparing among different approaches is straightforward: the algorithm providing the best fitness function is the winner. However, for an MOP, each metaheuristic provides a set of non-dominated solutions called Pareto front. Comparing among different fronts is not simple. To this end, we consider three different tools: hypervolume, set coverage, and attainment surface.

The hypervolume measures the portion of the objective space dominated by a front. Thus, given a front A and a reference point $r = (r_1, r_2, \dots, r_k)$, where k is the number of objectives the problem considers, each member of A has a hypercube associated denoted by

$$h(a) = [a_1, r_1] \times [a_2, r_2] \times \dots \times [a_k, r_k] \quad a \in A, \quad (18)$$

where a_i and r_i , with $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, k\}$, are the value of the i -th fitness function of a and the reference value of the i -th objective function, respectively. Thus, the hypervolume of A is the union of all its hypercubes. That is,

$$\text{hyp}(A, r) = \Lambda \left(\bigcup_{a \in A} h(a) \right), \quad (19)$$

where Λ is the Lebesgue measure. Before computing this metric, the values of the fitness functions are normalised to the interval $[0,1]$. Accordingly, we consider as reference point $r=(0,1)$. That is, f_1 is to minimise and f_2 is to maximise. The points assumed to perform the normalisation are shown in Table 2, where *ideal* and *nadir* are the best and the worst value of the fitness functions. These points were experimentally obtained.

The set coverage is a metric based on the dominance concept. Given two fronts A and B , $SC(A, B)$ calculates the percentage of solutions from B , which are weakly dominated by A . That is,

$$SC(A, B) = \frac{|\{b \in B / \exists a \in A : a \succeq b\}|}{|B|}. \quad (20)$$

Evolution of the energy charge of the sensors over time (J)																	f_1	f_2	A(t)	t
#1	#2	#3	#4	#5	#6	#7	#8	#9	#10	#11	#12	#13	#14	#15						
4.9886	4.9554	4.8401	4.8637	4.7856	4.8237	4.9659	4.8169	4.9743	4.7050	4.9476	4.9131	4.7280	4.9823	4.8480	0.1241	91.94%	91.94%	1		
4.9771	4.9109	4.6802	4.7274	4.5711	4.6475	4.9318	4.6338	4.9486	4.4101	4.8951	4.8261	4.4560	4.6959	4.6959	0.1241	91.94%	91.94%	2		
4.9657	4.8663	4.5203	4.5911	4.3567	4.4712	4.8978	4.4508	4.9229	4.1151	4.8427	4.7392	4.1840	4.9468	4.5439	0.1241	91.94%	91.94%	3		
4.9543	4.8217	4.3604	4.4547	4.1423	4.2949	4.8637	4.2677	4.8972	3.8201	4.7903	4.6523	3.9120	4.9291	4.3918	0.1241	91.94%	91.94%	4		
4.9429	4.7772	4.2005	4.3184	3.9278	4.1187	4.8296	4.0846	4.8715	3.5252	4.7379	4.5654	3.6400	4.9114	4.2398	0.1241	91.94%	91.94%	5		
4.9314	4.7326	4.0406	4.1821	3.7134	3.9424	4.7955	3.9015	4.8459	3.2302	4.6854	4.4784	3.3680	4.8937	4.0877	0.1241	91.94%	91.94%	6		
4.9200	4.6880	3.8806	4.0458	3.4990	3.7661	4.7614	3.7184	4.8202	2.9352	4.6330	4.3915	3.0960	4.8760	3.9357	0.1241	91.94%	91.94%	7		
4.9086	4.6435	3.7207	3.9095	3.2845	3.5899	4.7274	3.5353	4.7945	2.6403	4.5806	4.3046	2.8240	4.8582	3.7837	0.1241	91.94%	91.94%	8		
4.8971	4.5989	3.5608	3.7732	3.0701	3.4136	4.6933	3.3523	4.7688	2.3453	4.5281	4.2177	2.5520	4.8405	3.6316	0.1241	91.94%	91.94%	9		
4.8857	4.5544	3.4009	3.6369	2.8557	3.2373	4.6392	3.1692	4.7431	2.0504	4.4757	4.1307	2.2800	4.8228	3.4796	0.1241	91.94%	91.94%	10		
4.8743	4.5098	3.2410	3.5005	2.6412	3.0611	4.6251	2.9861	4.7174	1.7554	4.4233	4.0438	2.0080	4.8051	3.3275	0.1241	91.94%	91.94%	11		
4.8628	4.4652	3.0811	3.3642	2.4268	2.8848	4.5911	2.8030	4.6917	1.4604	4.3709	3.9569	1.7360	4.7873	3.1755	0.1241	91.94%	91.94%	12		
4.8514	4.4207	2.9212	3.2279	2.2124	2.7085	4.5570	2.6199	4.6660	1.1655	4.3184	3.8700	1.4640	4.7696	3.0234	0.1241	91.94%	91.94%	13		
4.8400	4.3761	2.7613	3.0916	1.9979	2.5323	4.5229	2.4369	4.6403	0.8705	4.2660	3.7830	1.1920	4.7519	2.8714	0.1241	91.94%	91.94%	14		
4.8286	4.3315	2.6014	2.9553	1.7835	2.3560	4.4888	2.2538	4.6146	0.5755	4.2136	3.6961	0.9200	4.7342	2.7193	0.1241	91.94%	91.94%	15		
4.8171	4.2870	2.4415	2.8190	1.5691	2.1798	4.4547	2.0707	4.5800	0.2806	4.1611	3.6092	0.6480	4.7165	2.5673	0.1241	91.94%	91.94%	16		
4.8057	4.2424	2.2816	2.6826	1.3546	2.0035	4.4207	1.8876	4.5633	0.0000	4.1087	3.5222	0.3760	4.6987	2.4153	0.1241	91.94%	91.94%	17		
4.7943	4.1978	2.1217	2.5463	1.1402	1.8272	4.3866	1.7045	4.5376	0.0000	4.0563	3.4353	0.1040	4.6810	2.2632	0.1234	91.61%	85.95%	18		
4.7828	4.1533	1.9618	2.4100	0.9258	1.6510	4.3525	1.5215	4.5119	0.0000	4.0039	3.3484	0.0000	4.6633	2.1112	0.1228	91.31%	85.95%	19		
4.7714	4.1087	1.8018	2.2737	0.7113	1.4747	4.3184	1.3384	4.4862	0.0000	3.9514	3.2615	0.0000	4.6456	1.9591	0.1217	90.72%	79.60%	20		
4.7600	4.0641	1.6419	2.1374	0.4969	1.2984	4.2843	1.1553	4.4605	0.0000	3.8980	3.1745	0.0000	4.6279	1.8071	0.1206	90.19%	79.60%	21		
4.7486	4.0196	1.4820	2.0011	0.2825	1.1222	4.2503	0.9722	4.4348	0.0000	3.8466	3.0876	0.0000	4.6101	1.6550	0.1197	89.71%	79.60%	22		
4.7371	3.9750	1.3221	1.8648	0.0680	0.9459	4.2162	0.7891	4.4091	0.0000	3.7941	3.0007	0.0000	4.5924	1.5030	0.1188	89.27%	79.60%	23		
4.7257	3.9305	1.1622	1.7284	0.0000	0.7696	4.1821	0.6060	4.3834	0.0000	3.7417	2.9138	0.0000	4.5747	1.3510	0.1180	88.87%	79.60%	24		
4.7143	3.8859	1.0023	1.5921	0.0000	0.5934	4.1480	0.4230	4.3577	0.0000	3.6893	2.8268	0.0000	4.5570	1.1989	0.1169	88.24%	73.19%	25		
4.7028	3.8413	0.8424	1.4558	0.0000	0.4171	4.1140	0.2399	4.3321	0.0000	3.6369	2.7399	0.0000	4.5393	1.0469	0.1158	87.66%	73.19%	26		
4.6914	3.7968	0.6825	1.3195	0.0000	0.2408	4.0799	0.0568	4.3064	0.0000	3.5844	2.6530	0.0000	4.5215	0.8948	0.1149	87.13%	73.19%	27		
4.6800	3.7522	0.5226	1.1832	0.0000	0.0646	4.0458	0.0000	4.2807	0.0000	3.5320	2.5660	0.0000	4.5038	0.7428	0.1140	86.63%	73.19%	28		
4.6685	3.7076	0.3627	1.0469	0.0000	0.0000	4.0117	0.0000	4.2550	0.0000	3.4796	2.4791	0.0000	4.4861	0.5907	0.1129	85.99%	68.13%	29		

Parameters of the example

$\tilde{S}_s$	Instance 100x100.15.60
$\tilde{S}_r$	{(20,20)}
$\tilde{s}_r$	1

Fig. 5: Illustrative example of the RNPP definition.

Table 2: Hypervolume reference points.

instance	Ref f_1		Ref f_2		instance	Ref f_1		Ref f_2	
	ideal	nadir	ideal	nadir		ideal	nadir	ideal	nadir
50x50.15.30	0.02	0.04	100%	60%	50x50.15.60	0.02	0.04	100%	60%
100x100.15.30	0.02	0.12	100%	60%	100x100.15.60	0.02	0.16	100%	60%
200x200.15.30	0.10	0.30	100%	60%	200x200.15.60	0.10	0.40	100%	60%
300x300.15.30	0.04	0.50	100%	60%	300x300.15.60	0.04	0.64	100%	60%

Table 3: Parametric sweep.

NSGA-II			SPEA2		
Parameter	Value	Range	Parameter	Value	Range
$mutP$	0.50	[0.05,0.1,0.15,...,0.95]	$mutP$	0.50	[0.05,0.1,0.15,...,0.95]
$crossP$	0.50	[0.05,0.1,0.15,...,0.95]	$crossP$	0.50	[0.05,0.1,0.15,...,0.95]

MO-VNS			MO-VNS.PER		
Parameter	Value	Range	Parameter	Value	Range
n_s	7	[4,5,6,...,14]	$mutP$	0.10	[0.05,0.1,0.15,...,0.95]
dv	2	[1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9]	n_s	11	[4,5,6,...,14]
			dv	3	[1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9]

The attainment surface is a graphical tool for representing fronts. It draws a boundary in the objective space, separating those points which are dominated, from those which are not dominated. This approach is useful when we want to display several fronts in a same plot, e.g. to compare among different algorithms. Usually, figures showing multiple fronts without considering attainment surface are confusing and misleading.

6.4 Configuring the algorithms

Before performing the experiments, all the algorithms were adequately configured. To this end, we follow an habitual strategy: starting from default values, a parameter of the algorithm is selected to be tuned. Then, 31 independent runs are performed for each value of the parameter, assuming 50 000 evaluations. The value of the parameter providing the best performance on aver-

age is selected, considering the hypervolume metric to this end. Next, another parameter is selected so long as all of them are fixed. Table 3 shows the range of values considered for each algorithm, as well as the value selected. As population size, a same habitual value of 100 individuals is assumed for all the algorithms.

7 Discussion of the results obtained

In this section, we apply the metaheuristics to solve the data set. The results obtained are analysed from two different viewpoints. On the one hand, we study the quality of the solutions obtained in MO terms. On the other hand, we analyse the advantages provided by the addition of routers to traditional WSNs.

7.1 Multiobjective analysis

Tables 4 and 5 show average hypervolume and InterQuartile Range (IQR) for each algorithm, test case, and stop condition. In these tables, higher hypervolumes for each test case and stop condition are shaded. Analysing these values, some algorithms seem to provide better performance than others. However, we do not know if the differences are significant. To check this, we follow a widely accepted statistical methodology. Firstly, we analyse if data come from a normal distribution. To this end, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov-Lilliefors's (Lilliefors (1967)) and Shapiro-Wilk's (Shapiro and Wilk (1965)) tests are considered with hypothesis: H_0 if data follow a Gaussian distribution and H_1 otherwise. P-values lower than 0.05

were obtained for all the cases. Hence, we cannot assume H_0 and the median (Me) is the average value.

The next step is to study if there are significant differences among the algorithms. As samples are independent and data do not follow a normal distribution, in line with the previous step, we consider the Wilcoxon-Mann-Whitney's test (Mann and Whitney (1947)) with hypotheses: H_0 Me_i is lower or equal than Me_j and H_1 Me_i is greater than Me_j , with $i = 1, 2, \dots, 4$, $j = 2, 3, 4$, $i < j$, 1=MOVNS, 2=MOVNS_PER, 3=NSGA-II, and 4=SPEA2. The p-values obtained are analysed considering a significance level of 0.05. Statistical conclusions reached appear in the subtable *statistical analysis* of Tables 4 and 5. In this analysis, we show the algorithms providing the best significant performance for each stop condition and test case. Note that, if several algorithms provide the best performance for a same stop condition and test case, it means that there are not significant differences between them. However, they are significantly better than the remainder algorithms.

Based on this statistical analysis, Figure 6 shows the percentage of test cases in which the algorithms provide the best significant performance, considering four different cases attending to the size of the surface. In this figure and for 50x50 scenarios, we note that MO-VNS_PER provides the best behaviour for reduced stop conditions, while MO-VNS is the best algorithm for high number of evaluations. For 100x100 scenarios, MO-VNS shows the best performance for all the stop conditions, followed by MO-VNS_PER. If we consider 200x200 scenarios, MO-VNS provides the best behaviour for reduced stop conditions. However, if the number of evaluations increases, MO-VNS_PER shows a similar behaviour. If we assume 300x300 scenarios, MO-VNS_PER provides the best performance for all the stop conditions, followed by NSGA-II and SPEA2. However, if the number of evaluations is increased, we note that NSGA-II provides a similar behaviour than MO-VNS_PER. Regarding to this analysis, we conclude that MO-VNS is the best algorithm for small and medium instances, followed by MO-VNS_PER. For big instances, MO-VNS_PER provides the best behaviour followed by NSGA-II. This means that MO-VNS needs additional information from perturbation mechanism to get good results due to the complexity of the instance.

As for hypervolume, we assume the set coverage metric to study the behaviour of the algorithms according to the size of the surface. This metric was calculated considering the median Pareto fronts from the distribution of 31 samples previously obtained. Thus, for 50x50 scenarios, Table 6 shows the average set coverage among the algorithms for each stop condition, providing MO-VNS the best behaviour on average, followed by MO-

VNS_PER. For 100x100 instances and as appear in Table 7, MO-VNS is the best algorithm followed by MO-VNS_PER. As Table 8 shows, MO-VNS_PER provides the best behaviour for 200x200 instances. Finally, for 300x300 scenarios, MO-VNS_PER shows the best average performance, followed by SPEA2 and NSGA-II.

Note that we reach similar conclusions for both MO metrics. MO-VNS provides the best performance for small and medium instances. However, if the complexity of the instance is increased, MO-VNS including perturbation provides the best performance. In both cases, these two versions of MO-VNS provide a better behaviour than standard NSGA-II and SPEA2. Finally, we assume the attainment surface tool to show some of these median Pareto fronts. To this end, we consider the test cases, having the highest number of relay nodes for each instance, with 800 000 evaluations. Analysing these plots, we graphically observe this behaviour.

7.2 Analysing the advantages of adding relay nodes

In this subsection, we discuss the advantages provided by the addition of routers to traditional WSNs. To this end, we show the extreme values of the median Pareto fronts obtained by MO-VNS_PER for 800 000 evaluations (see Table 10). As previously discussed, this algorithm provides a good behaviour solving the RNPP. Each extreme solution of MO-VNS_PER is associated with two different quality metrics, *gain* and *gain_r*, respectively. *gain* denotes the percentage in which a fitness function is increased (positive) or decreased (negative), regarding the use of a traditional WSN (see Fig. 3). *gain_r* is a measure of efficiency, it is a rate between *gain* and the number of routers considered. According to this table, the addition of relay nodes allows optimising traditional WSNs in a good way, e.g. f_1 is decreased by up to 91.52% and f_2 is increased by up to 17.10%. However, as table 10 shows, we must consider that this approach is limited, due to as the number of routers increases, the efficiency of the optimisation decreases.

8 Concluding remarks

In this paper, we study how to deploy relay nodes into previously-established static traditional WSNs, with the purpose of optimising two important features: average energy consumption of sensors and average sensitivity area provided by the WSN. As several authors proved, this is an NP-hard optimisation problem, hence it is habitual the use of non-conventional techniques. To this end, we assume two different approaches of the trajectory algorithm MO-VNS, including two additional

Table 4: Average hypervolumes obtained: 50x50, 100x100, and 200x200 instances.

NSGA-II($\overline{Hyp} \%, IQR$)										
Instance(routers)	25 000	50 000	100 000	200 000	300 000	400 000	500 000	600 000	700 000	800 000
50x50_15.30(1)	64.61%, 0.0000	64.61%, 0.0000	64.61%, 0.0000	64.61%, 0.0000	64.61%, 0.0000	64.61%, 0.0000	64.61%, 0.0000	64.61%, 0.0000	64.61%, 0.0000	64.61%, 0.0000
50x50_15.60(1)	64.61%, 0.0000	64.61%, 0.0000	64.61%, 0.0000	64.61%, 0.0000	64.61%, 0.0000	64.61%, 0.0000	64.61%, 0.0000	64.61%, 0.0000	64.61%, 0.0000	64.61%, 0.0000
100x100_15.30(1)	30.78%, 0.0026	30.86%, 0.0018	30.97%, 0.0000	30.97%, 0.0000	30.97%, 0.0000	30.97%, 0.0000	30.97%, 0.0000	30.97%, 0.0000	30.97%, 0.0000	30.97%, 0.0000
100x100_15.30(2)	49.37%, 0.0045	49.70%, 0.0031	49.90%, 0.0003	49.91%, 0.0002	49.92%, 0.0002	49.93%, 0.0002	49.93%, 0.0003	49.93%, 0.0003	49.94%, 0.0003	49.94%, 0.0003
100x100_15.30(3)	59.94%, 0.0030	60.16%, 0.0025	60.30%, 0.0004	60.43%, 0.0018	60.44%, 0.0035	60.47%, 0.0034	60.51%, 0.0047	60.53%, 0.0051	60.54%, 0.0051	60.55%, 0.0055
100x100_15.60(1)	27.83%, 0.0008	27.88%, 0.0001	27.89%, 0.0000	27.89%, 0.0000	27.89%, 0.0000	27.89%, 0.0000	27.89%, 0.0000	27.89%, 0.0000	27.89%, 0.0000	27.89%, 0.0000
100x100_15.60(2)	51.14%, 0.0039	51.36%, 0.0036	51.56%, 0.0035	51.66%, 0.0013	51.75%, 0.0000	51.75%, 0.0000	51.75%, 0.0000	51.75%, 0.0000	51.76%, 0.0000	51.76%, 0.0000
100x100_15.60(3)	66.80%, 0.0040	67.15%, 0.0031	67.41%, 0.0046	67.64%, 0.0040	67.77%, 0.0023	67.82%, 0.0025	67.87%, 0.0022	67.91%, 0.0022	67.93%, 0.0021	67.96%, 0.0019
200x200_15.30(1)	28.30%, 0.0085	28.91%, 0.0192	29.45%, 0.0149	30.24%, 0.0000	30.24%, 0.0000	30.24%, 0.0000	30.24%, 0.0000	30.24%, 0.0000	30.24%, 0.0000	30.24%, 0.0000
200x200_15.30(2)	35.31%, 0.0251	35.75%, 0.0184	36.77%, 0.0107	37.28%, 0.0054	37.55%, 0.0063	37.70%, 0.0066	37.63%, 0.0052	37.54%, 0.0048	37.94%, 0.0068	38.07%, 0.0062
200x200_15.30(4)	47.26%, 0.0402	48.87%, 0.0395	50.27%, 0.0280	51.86%, 0.0152	52.16%, 0.0159	52.30%, 0.0156	52.38%, 0.0161	52.45%, 0.0173	52.50%, 0.0137	52.52%, 0.0137
200x200_15.30(6)	61.37%, 0.0164	63.36%, 0.0194	64.68%, 0.0256	65.63%, 0.0221	65.91%, 0.0205	66.03%, 0.0219	66.14%, 0.0241	66.19%, 0.0246	66.29%, 0.0267	66.34%, 0.0233
200x200_15.30(9)	73.88%, 0.0185	75.85%, 0.0220	77.40%, 0.0163	78.38%, 0.0095	78.78%, 0.0145	78.96%, 0.0161	79.06%, 0.0183	79.13%, 0.0186	79.22%, 0.0199	79.29%, 0.0207
200x200_15.60(1)	24.32%, 0.0009	24.36%, 0.0007	24.42%, 0.0005	24.45%, 0.0005	24.45%, 0.0000	24.45%, 0.0000	24.45%, 0.0000	24.45%, 0.0000	24.45%, 0.0000	24.45%, 0.0000
200x200_15.60(2)	37.98%, 0.0066	38.29%, 0.0050	38.51%, 0.0041	38.84%, 0.0047	38.98%, 0.0036	39.12%, 0.0012	39.14%, 0.0042	39.17%, 0.0036	39.22%, 0.0037	39.26%, 0.0035
200x200_15.60(4)	62.73%, 0.0094	63.68%, 0.0061	64.39%, 0.0082	64.93%, 0.0040	65.07%, 0.0038	65.27%, 0.0058	65.39%, 0.0063	65.39%, 0.0055	65.45%, 0.0038	65.50%, 0.0060
200x200_15.60(6)	73.05%, 0.0110	73.99%, 0.0128	74.84%, 0.0124	75.56%, 0.0106	75.90%, 0.0112	76.18%, 0.0082	76.29%, 0.0089	76.43%, 0.0109	76.59%, 0.0109	76.69%, 0.0100
200x200_15.60(9)	81.70%, 0.0132	83.11%, 0.0096	84.36%, 0.0117	85.33%, 0.0109	85.67%, 0.0086	85.91%, 0.0107	86.04%, 0.0083	86.22%, 0.0094	86.32%, 0.0101	86.40%, 0.0086
SPEA2($\overline{Hyp} \%, IQR$)										
Instance(routers)	25 000	50 000	100 000	200 000	300 000	400 000	500 000	600 000	700 000	800 000
50x50_15.30(1)	64.61%, 0.0000	64.61%, 0.0000	64.61%, 0.0000	64.61%, 0.0000	64.61%, 0.0000	64.61%, 0.0000	64.61%, 0.0000	64.61%, 0.0000	64.61%, 0.0000	64.61%, 0.0000
50x50_15.60(1)	64.61%, 0.0000	64.61%, 0.0000	64.61%, 0.0000	64.61%, 0.0000	64.61%, 0.0000	64.61%, 0.0000	64.61%, 0.0000	64.61%, 0.0000	64.61%, 0.0000	64.61%, 0.0000
100x100_15.30(1)	30.75%, 0.0029	30.85%, 0.0020	30.97%, 0.0000	30.97%, 0.0000	30.97%, 0.0000	30.97%, 0.0000	30.97%, 0.0000	30.97%, 0.0000	30.97%, 0.0000	30.97%, 0.0000
100x100_15.30(2)	49.45%, 0.0051	49.67%, 0.0040	49.76%, 0.0029	49.92%, 0.0001	49.93%, 0.0002	49.93%, 0.0002	49.94%, 0.0003	49.94%, 0.0002	49.94%, 0.0002	49.94%, 0.0002
100x100_15.30(3)	59.48%, 0.0079	59.97%, 0.0035	60.24%, 0.0023	60.39%, 0.0027	60.48%, 0.0030	60.50%, 0.0040	60.52%, 0.0040	60.53%, 0.0040	60.57%, 0.0046	60.58%, 0.0044
100x100_15.60(1)	27.82%, 0.0012	27.88%, 0.0001	27.89%, 0.0000	27.89%, 0.0000	27.89%, 0.0000	27.89%, 0.0000	27.89%, 0.0000	27.89%, 0.0000	27.89%, 0.0000	27.89%, 0.0000
100x100_15.60(2)	51.14%, 0.0056	51.39%, 0.0049	51.57%, 0.0018	51.70%, 0.0011	51.74%, 0.0001	51.75%, 0.0001	51.75%, 0.0001	51.75%, 0.0001	51.75%, 0.0001	51.75%, 0.0001
100x100_15.60(3)	66.73%, 0.0051	67.14%, 0.0044	67.39%, 0.0024	67.62%, 0.0024	67.72%, 0.0016	67.76%, 0.0017	67.81%, 0.0017	67.85%, 0.0016	67.89%, 0.0012	67.92%, 0.0008
200x200_15.30(1)	28.61%, 0.0078	29.19%, 0.0164	29.63%, 0.0149	30.23%, 0.0001	30.24%, 0.0000	30.24%, 0.0000	30.24%, 0.0000	30.24%, 0.0000	30.24%, 0.0000	30.24%, 0.0000
200x200_15.30(2)	34.38%, 0.0267	35.64%, 0.0164	36.81%, 0.0109	37.55%, 0.0149	38.19%, 0.0186	38.51%, 0.0195	38.68%, 0.0190	38.91%, 0.0190	38.91%, 0.0175	38.99%, 0.0157
200x200_15.30(4)	46.04%, 0.0538	47.92%, 0.0344	50.02%, 0.0268	51.65%, 0.0197	52.27%, 0.0151	52.40%, 0.0125	52.75%, 0.0119	52.88%, 0.0117	52.95%, 0.0108	53.16%, 0.0113
200x200_15.30(6)	60.87%, 0.0224	62.94%, 0.0213	64.35%, 0.0168	65.13%, 0.0208	65.72%, 0.0177	65.93%, 0.0143	66.09%, 0.0161	66.18%, 0.0162	66.23%, 0.0159	66.29%, 0.0159
200x200_15.30(9)	72.90%, 0.0196	75.13%, 0.0145	76.98%, 0.0132	78.26%, 0.0130	78.62%, 0.0115	78.95%, 0.0104	79.24%, 0.0109	79.46%, 0.0120	79.57%, 0.0125	79.62%, 0.0103
200x200_15.60(1)	24.30%, 0.0009	24.36%, 0.0008	24.40%, 0.0004	24.44%, 0.0004	24.45%, 0.0000	24.45%, 0.0000	24.45%, 0.0000	24.45%, 0.0000	24.45%, 0.0000	24.45%, 0.0000
200x200_15.60(2)	38.15%, 0.0050	38.52%, 0.0039	38.69%, 0.0037	38.92%, 0.0039	39.14%, 0.0063	39.21%, 0.0053	39.26%, 0.0047	39.28%, 0.0037	39.30%, 0.0036	39.30%, 0.0036
200x200_15.60(4)	62.88%, 0.0086	63.84%, 0.0064	64.57%, 0.0051	65.06%, 0.0067	65.23%, 0.0060	65.33%, 0.0051	65.43%, 0.0054	65.51%, 0.0048	65.56%, 0.0039	65.61%, 0.0038
200x200_15.60(6)	72.36%, 0.0102	73.55%, 0.0140	74.49%, 0.0139	75.34%, 0.0087	75.71%, 0.0096	75.89%, 0.0110	76.04%, 0.0126	76.16%, 0.0103	76.27%, 0.0116	76.33%, 0.0125
200x200_15.60(9)	81.43%, 0.0144	83.06%, 0.0120	84.26%, 0.0077	84.86%, 0.0088	85.02%, 0.0084	85.07%, 0.0092	85.20%, 0.0102	85.23%, 0.0122	85.29%, 0.0112	85.29%, 0.0113
MO-VNS_PER($\overline{Hyp} \%, IQR$)										
Instance(routers)	25 000	50 000	100 000	200 000	300 000	400 000	500 000	600 000	700 000	800 000
50x50_15.30(1)	66.20%, 0.0086	66.79%, 0.0026	66.84%, 0.0020	66.88%, 0.0019	66.94%, 0.0021	66.98%, 0.0019	67.00%, 0.0012	67.01%, 0.0008	67.05%, 0.0004	67.05%, 0.0004
50x50_15.60(1)	66.20%, 0.0015	66.57%, 0.0060	66.79%, 0.0040	66.92%, 0.0020	66.96%, 0.0020	67.00%, 0.0011	67.05%, 0.0004	67.05%, 0.0003	67.06%, 0.0002	67.06%, 0.0002
100x100_15.30(1)	30.21%, 0.0183	30.57%, 0.0171	31.18%, 0.0089	31.29%, 0.0084	31.40%, 0.0050	31.44%, 0.0055	31.53%, 0.0040	31.64%, 0.0019	31.67%, 0.0023	31.70%, 0.0020
100x100_15.30(2)	48.19%, 0.0391	49.22%, 0.0340	50.52%, 0.0285	51.52%, 0.0303	51.53%, 0.0000	51.53%, 0.0000	51.53%, 0.0000	51.53%, 0.0000	51.53%, 0.0000	51.53%, 0.0000
100x100_15.30(3)	61.51%, 0.0165	61.91%, 0.0096	62.56%, 0.0010	62.57%, 0.0019	62.79%, 0.0031	62.92%, 0.0088	62.96%, 0.0087	63.02%, 0.0077	63.12%, 0.0070	63.16%, 0.0063
100x100_15.60(1)	27.56%, 0.0051	27.82%, 0.0050	27.97%, 0.0033	28.10%, 0.0033	28.15%, 0.0033	28.20%, 0.0019	28.25%, 0.0023	28.29%, 0.0015	28.30%, 0.0016	28.33%, 0.0012
100x100_15.60(2)	52.79%, 0.0049	52.99%, 0.0020	53.10%, 0.0000	53.10%, 0.0000	53.10%, 0.0000	53.15%, 0.0016	53.16%, 0.0018	53.19%, 0.0018	53.21%, 0.0018	53.22%, 0.0018
100x100_15.60(3)	67.94%, 0.0178	68.22%, 0.0140	68.59%, 0.0062	68.94%, 0.0040	69.16%, 0.0026	69.21%, 0.0021	69.33%, 0.0002	69.34%, 0.0002	69.35%, 0.0000	69.35%, 0.0000
200x200_15.30(1)	24.08%, 0.0639	29.05%, 0.0060	29.31%, 0.0005	29.32%, 0.0005	29.32%, 0.0005	29.34%, 0.0012	29.35%, 0.0017	29.35%, 0.0016	29.36%, 0.0016	29.37%, 0.0018
200x200_15.30(2)	34.26%, 0.0479	35.78%, 0.0612	36.96%, 0.0799	37.93%, 0.0805	38.59%, 0.0546	38.96%, 0.0237	41.11%, 0.0022	41.12%, 0.0023	41.12%, 0.0022	41.13%, 0.0022
200x200_15.30(4)	48.56%, 0.0879	50.25%, 0.0850	51.55%, 0.0487	52.54%, 0.0472	54.69%, 0.0203	54.83%, 0.0185	55.08%, 0.0159	55.66%, 0.0121	55.77%, 0.0106	55.44%, 0.0129
200x200_15.30(6)	64.63%, 0.0281	65.24%, 0.0350	66.64%, 0.0254	67.23%, 0.0234	67.59%, 0.0189	67.69%, 0.0198	67.87%, 0.0181	67.95%, 0.0180	68.04%, 0.0172	68.07%, 0.0170
200x200_15.30(9)	76.13%, 0.0225	77.60%, 0.0185	78.49%, 0.0243	79.29%, 0.0222	79.58%, 0.0221	79.78%, 0.0218	79.96%, 0.0191	80.13%, 0.0199	80.31%, 0.0192	80.52%, 0.0178
200x200_15.60(1)	23.73%, 0.0157	24.10%, 0.0142	24.31%, 0.0091	24.43%, 0.0087	24.50%, 0.0070	24.58%, 0.0069	24.60%, 0.0069	24.63%, 0.0070	24.66%, 0.0069	24.68%, 0.0071
200x200_15.60(2)	37.36%, 0.0219	38.71%, 0.0129	39.00%, 0.0115	39.20%, 0.0080	39.22%, 0.0063	39.33%, 0.0067	39.35%, 0.0066	39.38%, 0.0067	39.43%, 0.0068	39.45%, 0.0068
200x200_15.60(4)	65.84%, 0.0056	66.19%, 0.0065	66.45%, 0.0067	66.68%, 0.0063	66.80%, 0.0059	66.94%, 0.0055	67.01%, 0.0041	67.10%, 0.0046	67.17%, 0.0036	67.20%, 0.0045
200x200_15.60(6)	75.59%, 0.0085	76.10%, 0.0131	76.52%, 0.0118	76.85%, 0.0184	77.03%, 0.0139	77.14%, 0.0169	77.22%, 0.0172	77.30%, 0.0149	77.37%, 0.0150	77.39%, 0.0149
200x200_15.60(9)	83.82%, 0.0115	84.60%, 0.0099	85.18%, 0.0139	85.6						

Table 5: Average hypervolumes obtained: 300x300 instances.

NSGA-II($\overline{Hyp} \%, IQR$)										
Instance(routers)	25 000	50 000	100 000	200 000	300 000	400 000	500 000	600 000	700 000	800 000
300x300.15.30(2)	29.69%, 0.0052	30.03%, 0.0061	30.30%, 0.0045	30.57%, 0.0046	30.72%, 0.0053	30.82%, 0.0045	30.87%, 0.0040	30.91%, 0.0034	30.94%, 0.0034	30.98%, 0.0037
300x300.15.30(4)	34.38%, 0.0077	35.08%, 0.0073	35.54%, 0.0066	36.12%, 0.0082	36.34%, 0.0055	36.51%, 0.0074	36.64%, 0.0075	36.75%, 0.0079	36.81%, 0.0079	36.87%, 0.0080
300x300.15.30(6)	38.23%, 0.0119	39.26%, 0.0111	39.93%, 0.0108	40.66%, 0.0139	40.96%, 0.0124	41.20%, 0.0130	41.40%, 0.0111	41.52%, 0.0103	41.60%, 0.0110	41.69%, 0.0099
300x300.15.30(12)	44.39%, 0.0206	46.32%, 0.0155	47.67%, 0.0168	48.75%, 0.0130	49.20%, 0.0135	49.46%, 0.0121	49.66%, 0.0108	49.83%, 0.0102	50.01%, 0.0088	50.09%, 0.0087
300x300.15.30(18)	47.58%, 0.0114	50.03%, 0.0183	51.60%, 0.0126	52.94%, 0.0107	53.81%, 0.0094	54.30%, 0.0058	54.63%, 0.0076	54.75%, 0.0061	55.69%, 0.0138	56.17%, 0.0328
300x300.15.30(24)	51.30%, 0.0465	55.82%, 0.0661	58.10%, 0.0701	59.54%, 0.0905	61.08%, 0.0823	62.08%, 0.0869	62.62%, 0.0846	63.21%, 0.0642	63.86%, 0.0580	64.13%, 0.0590
300x300.15.60(2)	22.79%, 0.0039	23.04%, 0.0026	23.23%, 0.0029	23.33%, 0.0017	23.42%, 0.0017	23.47%, 0.0026	23.53%, 0.0026	23.56%, 0.0030	23.58%, 0.0035	23.60%, 0.0035
300x300.15.60(4)	34.27%, 0.0059	34.80%, 0.0074	35.37%, 0.0061	35.65%, 0.0056	35.86%, 0.0055	35.98%, 0.0084	36.06%, 0.0068	36.15%, 0.0065	36.20%, 0.0059	36.25%, 0.0064
300x300.15.60(6)	42.00%, 0.0090	43.01%, 0.0055	43.67%, 0.0041	44.24%, 0.0049	44.51%, 0.0041	44.75%, 0.0078	44.89%, 0.0056	44.98%, 0.0063	45.07%, 0.0075	45.19%, 0.0072
300x300.15.60(12)	57.91%, 0.0123	59.07%, 0.0117	60.00%, 0.0096	61.00%, 0.0043	61.15%, 0.0056	61.35%, 0.0079	61.56%, 0.0093	61.68%, 0.0092	61.82%, 0.0125	61.91%, 0.0090
300x300.15.60(18)	64.31%, 0.0109	65.38%, 0.0032	66.50%, 0.0109	67.57%, 0.0070	67.96%, 0.0095	68.31%, 0.0107	68.57%, 0.0100	68.79%, 0.0083	68.94%, 0.0089	69.15%, 0.0106
300x300.15.60(24)	67.16%, 0.0093	68.38%, 0.0073	69.82%, 0.0082	71.06%, 0.0051	71.75%, 0.0051	72.20%, 0.0087	72.49%, 0.0055	72.71%, 0.0058	72.90%, 0.0070	72.91%, 0.0060
SPEA2($\overline{Hyp} \%, IQR$)										
Instance(routers)	25 000	50 000	100 000	200 000	300 000	400 000	500 000	600 000	700 000	800 000
300x300.15.30(2)	29.62%, 0.0036	30.02%, 0.0049	30.29%, 0.0063	30.54%, 0.0066	30.74%, 0.0030	30.85%, 0.0020	30.94%, 0.0013	30.98%, 0.0026	31.00%, 0.0027	31.04%, 0.0026
300x300.15.30(4)	34.40%, 0.0104	35.21%, 0.0067	35.77%, 0.0062	36.30%, 0.0080	36.62%, 0.0055	36.86%, 0.0042	36.97%, 0.0026	37.00%, 0.0033	37.06%, 0.0038	37.12%, 0.0040
300x300.15.30(6)	37.70%, 0.0127	39.04%, 0.0150	40.13%, 0.0153	40.94%, 0.0172	41.38%, 0.0176	41.68%, 0.0171	41.87%, 0.0151	41.98%, 0.0174	42.10%, 0.0168	42.18%, 0.0162
300x300.15.30(12)	42.74%, 0.0270	45.41%, 0.0181	47.05%, 0.0162	48.05%, 0.0133	48.63%, 0.0120	48.96%, 0.0125	49.12%, 0.0118	49.28%, 0.0126	49.48%, 0.0139	49.63%, 0.0113
300x300.15.30(18)	45.53%, 0.0177	49.05%, 0.0102	52.13%, 0.0192	54.13%, 0.0288	55.01%, 0.0332	55.60%, 0.0411	56.07%, 0.0407	56.37%, 0.0436	56.67%, 0.0435	56.82%, 0.0434
300x300.15.30(24)	49.15%, 0.0246	54.00%, 0.0486	58.12%, 0.0647	60.70%, 0.0671	61.76%, 0.0720	62.60%, 0.0673	63.32%, 0.0458	63.72%, 0.0444	64.07%, 0.0448	64.26%, 0.0362
300x300.15.60(2)	22.77%, 0.0046	23.06%, 0.0038	23.35%, 0.0026	23.53%, 0.0021	23.64%, 0.0019	23.69%, 0.0020	23.73%, 0.0018	23.77%, 0.0017	23.80%, 0.0026	23.83%, 0.0026
300x300.15.60(4)	34.19%, 0.0062	34.87%, 0.0095	35.45%, 0.0086	35.84%, 0.0093	36.15%, 0.0079	36.15%, 0.0063	36.26%, 0.0063	36.31%, 0.0063	36.35%, 0.0065	36.40%, 0.0063
300x300.15.60(6)	41.69%, 0.0095	42.72%, 0.0093	43.60%, 0.0091	44.40%, 0.0104	44.79%, 0.0083	44.97%, 0.0119	45.06%, 0.0124	45.19%, 0.0096	45.26%, 0.0096	45.34%, 0.0083
300x300.15.60(12)	57.45%, 0.0093	59.24%, 0.0094	60.52%, 0.0087	61.40%, 0.0079	61.60%, 0.0041	61.86%, 0.0054	61.91%, 0.0080	62.22%, 0.0054	62.19%, 0.0061	62.26%, 0.0055
300x300.15.60(18)	63.63%, 0.0145	65.00%, 0.0016	66.21%, 0.0073	67.52%, 0.0111	68.13%, 0.0094	68.53%, 0.0049	68.71%, 0.0067	68.88%, 0.0090	69.05%, 0.0117	69.09%, 0.0121
300x300.15.60(24)	66.52%, 0.0098	67.80%, 0.0073	69.26%, 0.0128	70.67%, 0.0148	71.49%, 0.0103	71.93%, 0.0113	72.30%, 0.0082	72.62%, 0.0106	72.75%, 0.0092	72.87%, 0.0089
MO-VNS_PER($\overline{Hyp} \%, IQR$)										
Instance(routers)	25 000	50 000	100 000	200 000	300 000	400 000	500 000	600 000	700 000	800 000
300x300.15.30(2)	30.36%, 0.0095	30.65%, 0.0081	30.92%, 0.0067	31.25%, 0.0064	31.39%, 0.0045	31.47%, 0.0030	31.54%, 0.0022	31.57%, 0.0027	31.60%, 0.0021	31.65%, 0.0015
300x300.15.30(4)	35.79%, 0.0146	36.48%, 0.0085	36.93%, 0.0049	37.21%, 0.0052	37.40%, 0.0070	37.48%, 0.0052	37.55%, 0.0056	37.67%, 0.0064	37.73%, 0.0080	37.78%, 0.0079
300x300.15.30(6)	40.32%, 0.0173	41.22%, 0.0220	41.80%, 0.0217	42.19%, 0.0213	42.39%, 0.0211	42.51%, 0.0213	42.66%, 0.0184	42.78%, 0.0188	42.80%, 0.0190	42.82%, 0.0190
300x300.15.30(12)	46.33%, 0.0175	47.08%, 0.0080	47.80%, 0.0046	48.36%, 0.0032	48.58%, 0.0034	48.73%, 0.0044	48.99%, 0.0039	49.11%, 0.0036	49.14%, 0.0030	49.22%, 0.0031
300x300.15.30(18)	50.12%, 0.0099	51.23%, 0.0120	52.38%, 0.0145	52.98%, 0.0112	53.39%, 0.0065	53.58%, 0.0099	53.71%, 0.0104	53.87%, 0.0114	53.94%, 0.0122	54.05%, 0.0120
300x300.15.30(24)	55.14%, 0.0302	56.50%, 0.0195	57.51%, 0.0192	58.05%, 0.0121	58.62%, 0.0105	58.87%, 0.0098	59.17%, 0.0107	59.30%, 0.0096	59.50%, 0.0108	59.57%, 0.0108
300x300.15.60(2)	23.78%, 0.0062	24.02%, 0.0049	24.12%, 0.0036	24.22%, 0.0021	24.26%, 0.0019	24.28%, 0.0013	24.30%, 0.0016	24.32%, 0.0016	24.34%, 0.0016	24.37%, 0.0016
300x300.15.60(4)	35.86%, 0.0141	36.41%, 0.0084	36.72%, 0.0068	37.02%, 0.0067	37.19%, 0.0058	37.35%, 0.0055	37.44%, 0.0068	37.47%, 0.0078	37.52%, 0.0080	37.55%, 0.0079
300x300.15.60(6)	43.83%, 0.0097	44.43%, 0.0099	44.96%, 0.0055	45.38%, 0.0075	45.55%, 0.0077	45.72%, 0.0083	45.77%, 0.0081	45.84%, 0.0084	45.93%, 0.0104	45.98%, 0.0088
300x300.15.60(12)	59.07%, 0.0070	59.96%, 0.0170	60.63%, 0.0067	61.11%, 0.0071	61.33%, 0.0057	61.61%, 0.0049	61.72%, 0.0071	61.85%, 0.0081	62.02%, 0.0079	62.06%, 0.0079
300x300.15.60(18)	64.44%, 0.0042	64.96%, 0.0074	65.43%, 0.0093	65.92%, 0.0059	66.37%, 0.0018	66.37%, 0.0018	66.26%, 0.0029	66.39%, 0.0021	66.49%, 0.0038	66.55%, 0.0054
300x300.15.60(24)	67.68%, 0.0078	68.21%, 0.0059	68.83%, 0.0087	69.37%, 0.0082	69.71%, 0.0053	69.95%, 0.0059	70.11%, 0.0071	70.26%, 0.0052	70.41%, 0.0076	70.78%, 0.0065
MO-VNS($\overline{Hyp} \%, IQR$)										
Instance(routers)	25 000	50 000	100 000	200 000	300 000	400 000	500 000	600 000	700 000	800 000
300x300.15.30(2)	30.98%, 0.0031	31.15%, 0.0026	31.33%, 0.0016	31.50%, 0.0012	31.59%, 0.0019	31.63%, 0.0018	31.68%, 0.0012	31.69%, 0.0010	31.71%, 0.0008	31.71%, 0.0006
300x300.15.30(4)	35.53%, 0.0092	35.92%, 0.0125	36.35%, 0.0115	36.84%, 0.0126	37.18%, 0.0155	37.36%, 0.0117	37.43%, 0.0117	37.49%, 0.0109	37.56%, 0.0095	37.61%, 0.0093
300x300.15.30(6)	38.61%, 0.0114	39.29%, 0.0115	40.20%, 0.0152	40.90%, 0.0211	41.39%, 0.0279	41.63%, 0.0306	41.77%, 0.0290	41.89%, 0.0266	41.99%, 0.0282	42.10%, 0.0270
300x300.15.30(12)	44.16%, 0.0079	45.17%, 0.0131	46.32%, 0.0069	47.47%, 0.0087	47.99%, 0.0080	48.41%, 0.0074	48.65%, 0.0072	48.81%, 0.0080	49.03%, 0.0080	49.16%, 0.0088
300x300.15.30(18)	47.07%, 0.0129	48.44%, 0.0101	49.47%, 0.0074	50.51%, 0.0085	51.11%, 0.0143	51.63%, 0.0114	51.95%, 0.0073	52.20%, 0.0070	52.33%, 0.0073	52.62%, 0.0074
300x300.15.30(24)	49.23%, 0.0077	50.54%, 0.0105	51.88%, 0.0128	52.92%, 0.0179	53.75%, 0.0172	54.28%, 0.0167	54.70%, 0.0230	54.92%, 0.0204	55.16%, 0.0207	55.35%, 0.0216
300x300.15.60(2)	24.01%, 0.0028	24.09%, 0.0033	24.17%, 0.0028	24.26%, 0.0030	24.28%, 0.0022	24.30%, 0.0019	24.34%, 0.0012	24.34%, 0.0012	24.36%, 0.0011	24.38%, 0.0016
300x300.15.60(4)	35.66%, 0.0095	36.04%, 0.0090	36.33%, 0.0142	36.66%, 0.0113	36.81%, 0.0111	36.88%, 0.0107	36.97%, 0.0109	37.04%, 0.0106	37.08%, 0.0105	37.18%, 0.0095
300x300.15.60(6)	41.52%, 0.0279	42.27%, 0.0288	42.70%, 0.0262	43.48%, 0.0270	43.82%, 0.0260	44.36%, 0.0157	44.48%, 0.0136	44.65%, 0.0195	44.71%, 0.0189	44.80%, 0.0192
300x300.15.60(12)	55.87%, 0.0174	57.00%, 0.0114	58.47%, 0.0064	59.60%, 0.0144	60.05%, 0.0174	60.38%, 0.0213	60.52%, 0.0197	60.73%, 0.0131	60.77%, 0.0124	60.91%, 0.0081
300x300.15.60(18)	62.86%, 0.0142	63.73%, 0.0137	64.64%, 0.0105	65.44%, 0.0127	65.97%, 0.0111	66.27%, 0.0149	66.48%, 0.0164	66.70%, 0.0182	66.80%, 0.0191	66.90%, 0.0178
300x300.15.60(24)	66.62%, 0.0114	67.47%, 0.0102	68.31%, 0.0098	69.04%, 0.0082	69.41%, 0.0065	69.64%, 0.0079	69.86%, 0.0084	69.98%, 0.0069	70.08%, 0.0088	70.22%, 0.0100
Statistical analysis: 1=MO-VNS, 2=MO-VNS_PER, 3=NSGA-II, and 4=SPEA2										
Instance(routers)	25 000	50 000	100 000	200 000	300 000	400 000	500 000	600 000	700 000	800 000
300x300.15.30(2)	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
300x300.15.30(4)	1,2	2	1,2	1,2	1,2	1,2	1,2	1,2	1,2	1,2
300x300.15.30(6)	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
300x300.15.30(12)	2	2	2,3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
300x300.15.30(18)	2	2	2,4	4	3,4	3,4	3,4	3,4	3,4	3,4
300x300.15.30(24)	2	2,4	2,3,4	3,4	3,4	3,4	3,4	3,4	3,4	3,4
300x300.15.60(2)	2,1	2,1	2,1	2,1	2,1	2,1	2,1	2,1	2,1	2,1
300x300.15.60(4)	2,1	2,1	2,1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
300x300.15.60(6)	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
300x300.15.60(12)	2	2	2,4	2,4,3	2,4	2,4	2,4,3	2,4	2,4,3	2,4,3
300x300.15.60(18)	2,3	2,3	3,4	3,4	3,4	3,4	3,4	3,4	3,4	3,4
300x300.15.60(24)	2	2,3	3	3,4	3,4	3,4	3,4	3,4	3,4	3,4

Fig. 6: Analysis of the p-values obtained considering the hypervolume metric.

Fig. 7: Comparing the median Pareto fronts obtained through attainment surface representation.

standard algorithms belonging to EC (NSGA-II and SPEA2), for comparison purposes.

The four metaheuristics are applied to solve a freely available data set proposed by ourselves. We did not find any testbed fitting this problem definition. Hence, the use of a public instance allows that this work can be enhanced and replicated by other authors. All the results obtained are analysed through a widely accepted

Table 6: Average set coverage among the algorithms for 50x50 instances.

SC(NSGA-II,i), i=SPEA2, MO-VNS_PER, and MO-VNS											
	25 000	50 000	100 000	200 000	300 000	400 000	500 000	600 000	700 000	800 000	Average
SPEA2	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%
MO-VNS_PER	63.33%	56.25%	34.82%	37.50%	50.00%	26.67%	13.89%	12.50%	12.70%	11.81%	31.95%
MO-VNS	20.00%	20.00%	20.00%	20.00%	20.00%	20.00%	20.00%	20.00%	20.00%	20.00%	20.00%
Average	61.11%	58.75%	51.61%	52.50%	56.67%	48.89%	44.63%	44.17%	44.23%	43.94%	50.65%
SC(SPEA2,i), i=NSGA-II, MO-VNS_PER, and MO-VNS											
	25 000	50 000	100 000	200 000	300 000	400 000	500 000	600 000	700 000	800 000	Average
NSGAI	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%
MO-VNS_PER	63.33%	56.25%	34.82%	37.50%	50.00%	26.67%	13.89%	12.50%	12.70%	11.81%	31.95%
MO-VNS	20.00%	20.00%	20.00%	20.00%	20.00%	20.00%	20.00%	20.00%	20.00%	20.00%	20.00%
Average	61.11%	58.75%	51.61%	52.50%	56.67%	48.89%	44.63%	44.17%	44.23%	43.94%	50.65%
SC(MO-VNS_PER,i), i=NSGA-II, SPEA2, and MO-VNS											
	25 000	50 000	100 000	200 000	300 000	400 000	500 000	600 000	700 000	800 000	Average
NSGAI	38.89%	27.78%	55.56%	61.11%	55.56%	61.11%	72.22%	94.44%	94.44%	100.00%	66.11%
SPEA2	38.89%	27.78%	55.56%	61.11%	55.56%	61.11%	72.22%	94.44%	94.44%	100.00%	66.11%
MO-VNS	35.00%	35.00%	60.00%	45.00%	50.00%	50.00%	80.00%	80.00%	90.00%	95.00%	62.00%
Average	37.59%	30.19%	57.04%	55.74%	53.70%	57.41%	74.81%	89.63%	92.96%	98.33%	64.74%
SC(MO-VNS,i), i=NSGA-II, SPEA2, and MO-VNS_PER											
	25 000	50 000	100 000	200 000	300 000	400 000	500 000	600 000	700 000	800 000	Average
NSGAI	88.89%	88.89%	88.89%	88.89%	88.89%	88.89%	88.89%	88.89%	88.89%	88.89%	88.89%
SPEA2	88.89%	88.89%	88.89%	88.89%	88.89%	88.89%	88.89%	88.89%	88.89%	88.89%	88.89%
MO-VNS_PER	81.67%	81.25%	86.61%	79.17%	88.89%	81.67%	86.11%	87.50%	87.30%	88.19%	84.84%
Average	86.48%	86.34%	88.13%	85.65%	88.89%	86.48%	87.96%	88.43%	88.36%	88.66%	87.54%

Table 7: Average set coverage among the algorithms for 100x100 instances.

SC(NSGA-II,i), i=SPEA2, MO-VNS_PER, and MO-VNS											
	25 000	50 000	100 000	200 000	300 000	400 000	500 000	600 000	700 000	800 000	Average
SPEA2	48.93%	56.91%	70.99%	72.01%	77.34%	70.15%	77.52%	79.63%	82.10%	81.88%	71.74%
MO-VNS_PER	6.48%	14.89%	14.81%	15.61%	15.28%	5.45%	4.58%	5.58%	10.60%	5.87%	9.92%
MO-VNS	23.61%	13.08%	13.89%	6.43%	11.00%	8.45%	8.57%	9.79%	8.95%	8.16%	11.19%
Average	26.34%	28.29%	33.23%	31.35%	34.54%	28.02%	30.22%	31.66%	33.88%	31.97%	30.95%
SC(SPEA2,i), i=NSGA-II, MO-VNS_PER, and MO-VNS											
	25 000	50 000	100 000	200 000	300 000	400 000	500 000	600 000	700 000	800 000	Average
NSGAI	50.32%	57.19%	56.77%	72.15%	77.58%	78.90%	76.05%	79.76%	80.48%	79.45%	70.87%
MO-VNS_PER	16.33%	15.96%	15.93%	14.44%	15.28%	5.45%	4.58%	5.58%	9.73%	6.67%	11.00%
MO-VNS	34.57%	20.67%	20.56%	13.10%	17.43%	14.04%	15.00%	16.22%	15.38%	14.59%	18.16%
Average	33.74%	31.27%	31.08%	33.23%	36.76%	32.80%	31.88%	33.85%	35.20%	33.57%	33.34%
SC(MO-VNS_PER,i), i=NSGA-II, SPEA2, and MO-VNS											
	25 000	50 000	100 000	200 000	300 000	400 000	500 000	600 000	700 000	800 000	Average
NSGAI	67.60%	78.67%	77.49%	81.41%	81.93%	90.52%	86.77%	91.74%	87.06%	90.23%	83.34%
SPEA2	65.35%	73.38%	73.53%	83.26%	80.33%	91.78%	87.82%	92.84%	85.71%	88.51%	82.25%
MO-VNS	52.32%	50.28%	66.47%	54.84%	50.66%	67.73%	76.84%	82.33%	78.86%	87.76%	66.81%
Average	61.76%	67.44%	72.50%	73.17%	70.98%	83.34%	83.81%	88.97%	83.88%	88.83%	77.47%
SC(MO-VNS,i), i=NSGA-II, SPEA2, and MO-VNS_PER											
	25 000	50 000	100 000	200 000	300 000	400 000	500 000	600 000	700 000	800 000	Average
NSGAI	66.65%	81.40%	81.95%	89.79%	82.76%	87.34%	89.68%	88.41%	90.63%	91.99%	85.06%
SPEA2	61.54%	78.69%	82.04%	89.93%	82.05%	88.61%	89.80%	88.67%	89.28%	90.69%	84.13%
MO-VNS_PER	44.90%	68.17%	73.88%	85.57%	85.02%	90.09%	85.62%	84.37%	92.89%	94.64%	80.51%
Average	57.69%	76.09%	79.29%	88.43%	83.28%	88.68%	88.37%	87.15%	90.94%	92.44%	83.23%

Table 8: Average set coverage among the algorithms for 200x200 instances.

SC(NSGA-II,i), i=SPEA2, MO-VNS_PER, and MO-VNS											
	25 000	50 000	100 000	200 000	300 000	400 000	500 000	600 000	700 000	800 000	Average
SPEA2	38.65%	36.70%	52.50%	39.52%	49.39%	44.97%	37.90%	39.45%	32.55%	29.88%	40.15%
MO-VNS_PER	38.00%	19.71%	13.33%	13.61%	11.67%	15.48%	7.50%	8.93%	9.32%	13.97%	15.15%
MO-VNS	9.23%	16.90%	11.04%	12.10%	13.51%	11.07%	5.54%	4.68%	8.17%	4.56%	9.68%
Average	28.63%	24.44%	25.63%	21.74%	24.85%	23.84%	16.98%	17.69%	16.68%	16.14%	21.66%
SC(SPEA2,i), i=NSGA-II, MO-VNS_PER, and MO-VNS											
	25 000	50 000	100 000	200 000	300 000	400 000	500 000	600 000	700 000	800 000	Average
NSGAI	34.35%	37.80%	38.17%	55.79%	59.00%	55.19%	60.48%	58.53%	79.67%	82.29%	56.13%
MO-VNS_PER	40.00%	21.58%	13.33%	14.72%	14.54%	18.14%	8.93%	12.66%	13.94%	11.11%	16.90%
MO-VNS	3.72%	11.79%	8.75%	13.21%	3.74%	6.05%	6.21%	14.80%	15.52%	11.01%	9.48%
Average	26.02%	23.72%	20.08%	27.91%	25.76%	26.46%	25.21%	28.66%	36.38%	34.80%	27.50%
SC(MO-VNS_PER,i), i=NSGA-II, SPEA2, and MO-VNS											
	25 000	50 000	100 000	200 000	300 000	400 000	500 000	600 000	700 000	800 000	Average
NSGAI	59.67%	77.44%	77.83%	76.77%	85.16%	79.00%	87.52%	79.88%	83.75%	80.36%	78.74%
SPEA2	57.78%	67.51%	67.29%	78.42%	77.47%	80.87%	74.27%	74.18%	76.12%	76.12%	71.47%
MO-VNS	45.42%	47.27%	40.31%	60.04%	46.71%	52.89%	66.54%	62.16%	64.92%	65.49%	55.17%
Average	54.29%	61.84%	61.88%	68.04%	70.09%	69.79%	78.31%	72.10%	74.28%	73.99%	68.46%
SC(MO-VNS,i), i=NSGA-II, SPEA2, and MO-VNS_PER											
	25 000	50 000	100 000	200 000	300 000	400 000	500 000	600 000	700 000	800 000	Average
NSGAI	68.36%	77.50%	81.86%	80.95%	77.08%	77.32%	82.41%	84.37%	87.63%	88.77%	80.63%
SPEA2	73.67%	73.08%	81.57%	64.36%	76.85%	77.84%	76.55%	80.22%	69.39%	78.58%	75.21%
MO-VNS_PER	51.61%	48.48%	38.50%	34.36%	50.39%	52.22%	53.25%	55.47%	50.38%	48.45%	48.31%
Average	64.55%	66.35%	67.31%	59.89%	68.11%	69.13%	70.73%	73.35%	69.13%	71.93%	68.05%

Table 9: Average set coverage among the algorithms for 300x300 instances.

SC(NSGA-II,i), i=SPEA2, MO-VNS_PER, and MO-VNS											
	25 000	50 000	100 000	200 000	300 000	400 000	500 000	600 000	700 000	800 000	Average
SPEA2	66.99%	50.54%	46.31%	39.62%	37.09%	23.42%	28.21%	30.00%	22.56%	26.46%	37.12%
MO-VNS_PER	11.01%	10.50%	26.47%	31.85%	40.87%	32.39%	37.20%	36.54%	29.77%	28.61%	28.52%
MO-VNS	53.30%	55.03%	59.16%	57.69%	58.93%	59.36%	51.18%	50.12%	56.14%	48.91%	54.98%
Average	43.77%	38.69%	43.98%	43.05%	45.63%	38.39%	38.87%	38.88%	36.16%	34.66%	40.21%
SC(SPEA2,i), i=NSGA-II, MO-VNS_PER, and MO-VNS											
	25 000	50 000	100 000	200 000	300 000	400 000	500 000	600 000	700 000	800 000	Average
NSGAI	19.43%	32.24%	37.11%	44.47%	43.95%	44.64%	46.30%	51.90%	50.05%	50.89%	42.10%
MO-VNS_PER	3.62%	13.57%	27.38%	27.82%	31.71%	38.97%	45.92%	40.91%	39.51%	39.78%	30.92%
MO-VNS	30.74%	37.40%	53.89%	55.89%	52.01%	61.01%	55.64%	53.33%	55.47%	59.94%	51.53%
Average	17.93%	27.74%	39.46%	42.72%	42.55%	48.21%	49.29%	48.71%	48.34%	50.20%	41.52%
SC(MO-VNS_PER,i), i=NSGA-II, SPEA2, and MO-VNS											
	25 000	50 000	100 000	200 000	300 000	400 000	500 000	600 000	700 000	800 000	Average
NSGAI	83.43%	82.03%	60.13%	55.71%	48.22%	58.97%	48.24%	57.47%	59.92%	58.76%	61.29%
SPEA2	90.77%	74.05%	57.37%	57.40%	57.84%	32.24%	43.51%	50.10%	40.91%	41.23%	54.54%
MO-VNS	80.48%	71.74%	57.92%	58.97%	68.17%	63.97%	55.66%	65.21%	69.22%	66.27%	65.76%
Average	84.89%	75.94%	58.47%	57.36%	58.07%	51.73%	49.13%	57.59%	56.68%	55.42%	60.53%
SC(MO-VNS,i), i=NSGA-II, SPEA2, and MO-VNS_PER											
	25 000	50 000	100 000	200 000	300 000	400 000	500 000	600 000	700 000	800 000	Average
NSGAI	40.89%	37.87%	34.23%	31.63%	37.29%	37.05%	39.08%	41.25%	34.70%	38.51%	37.25%
SPEA2	57.17%	41.94%	37.65%	41.79%	38.55%	27.08%	29.59%	32.00%	28.64%	29.38%	36.38%
MO-VNS_PER	10.83%	18.79%	22.70%	25.04%	22.82%	22.59%	29.66%	21.14%	28.55%	29.74%	23.19%
Average	36.30%	32.87%	31.52%	32.82%	32.89%	28.91%	32.78%	31.46%	30.63%	32.54%	32.27%

Table 10: Extreme values obtained through MO-VNS_PER for 800 000 evaluations.

	extreme 1						extreme 2					
	f_1	$gain(f_1)$	$gain_+(f_1)$	f_2	$gain(f_2)$	$gain_+(f_2)$	f_1	$gain(f_1)$	$gain_+(f_1)$	f_2	$gain(f_2)$	$gain_+(f_2)$
50x50_15_30(1)	0.0286	-18.36%	-18.36%	92.05%	0.33%	0.33%	0.0229	-34.60%	-34.60%	88.98%	-3.02%	-3.02%
50x50_15_30(1)	0.0276	-21.08%	-21.08%	92.05%	0.33%	0.33%	0.0229	-34.60%	-34.60%	88.98%	-3.02%	-3.02%
100x100_15_30(1)	0.0946	-13.30%	-13.30%	90.55%	1.47%	1.47%	0.0780	-28.48%	-28.48%	88.88%	-0.41%	-0.41%
100x100_15_30(2)	0.0619	-43.25%	-21.62%	91.56%	2.60%	1.30%	0.0545	-50.02%	-25.01%	89.45%	0.23%	0.12%
100x100_15_30(3)	0.0469	-57.00%	-19.00%	91.61%	2.66%	0.89%	0.0401	-63.25%	-21.08%	81.95%	-8.16%	-2.72%
100x100_15_60(1)	0.1299	-12.35%	-12.35%	89.69%	3.53%	3.53%	0.1049	-29.21%	-29.21%	84.72%	-2.20%	-2.20%
100x100_15_60(2)	0.0914	-38.31%	-19.15%	91.26%	5.35%	2.67%	0.0616	-58.41%	-29.20%	81.27%	-6.18%	-3.09%
100x100_15_60(3)	0.0555	-62.54%	-20.85%	91.45%	5.57%	1.86%	0.0334	-77.47%	-25.82%	77.94%	-10.03%	-3.34%
200x200_15_30(1)	0.2390	-14.36%	-14.36%	88.54%	1.65%	1.65%	0.2167	-22.34%	-22.34%	85.73%	-1.57%	-1.57%
200x200_15_30(2)	0.2146	-25.10%	-11.55%	88.81%	1.97%	0.98%	0.156	-33.49%	-16.75%	87.75%	0.74%	0.37%
200x200_15_30(4)	0.1507	-45.99%	-11.50%	90.10%	3.44%	0.86%	0.1507	-45.99%	-11.50%	90.10%	3.44%	0.86%
200x200_15_30(6)	0.1320	-52.72%	-8.79%	90.80%	4.25%	0.71%	0.1206	-56.81%	-9.47%	89.42%	2.66%	0.44%
200x200_15_30(9)	0.0977	-64.99%	-7.22%	90.61%	4.02%	0.45%	0.0902	-67.70%	-7.52%	90.01%	3.34%	0.37%
200x200_15_60(1)	0.3107	-19.75%	-19.75%	86.60%	5.06%	5.06%	0.2875	-25.74%	-25.74%	86.14%	4.50%	4.50%
200x200_15_60(2)	0.2416	-37.60%	-18.80%	87.74%	6.44%	3.22%	0.2279	-41.14%	-20.57%	85.81%	4.10%	2.05%
200x200_15_60(4)	0.1528	-60.53%	-15.13%	90.70%	10.03%	2.51%	0.1344	-65.28%	-16.32%	86.61%	5.07%	1.27%
200x200_15_60(6)	0.1128	-70.87%	-11.81%	90.75%	10.09%	1.68%	0.0892	-76.95%	-12.83%	82.71%	0.34%	0.06%
200x200_15_60(9)	0.0629	-83.74%	-9.30%	89.98%	9.16%	1.02%	0.0580	-85.02%	-9.45%	85.63%	3.88%	0.43%
300x300_15_30(2)	0.3526	-16.53%	-8.27%	87.77%	14.82%	7.41%	0.2725	-35.50%	-17.75%	78.13%	2.21%	1.10%
300x300_15_30(4)	0.3206	-24.11%	-6.03%	88.27%	15.47%	3.87%	0.2449	-42.04%	-10.51%	79.51%	4.02%	1.00%
300x300_15_30(6)	0.3013	-28.69%	-4.73%	88.57%	15.87%	2.64%	0.2273	-46.19%	-7.70%	77.90%	2.02%	0.34%
300x300_15_30(12)	0.2033	-51.87%	-4.32%	89.02%	16.46%	1.37%	0.1861	-55.94%	-4.66%	78.69%	2.95%	0.25%
300x300_15_30(18)	0.1711	-59.49%	-3.31%	89.32%	16.85%	0.94%	0.1616	-61.76%	-3.43%	87.70%	14.72%	0.82%
300x300_15_30(24)	0.1422	-66.35%	-2.76%	89.51%	17.10%	0.71%	0.1296	-69.32%	-2.89%	88.91%	16.31%	0.68%
300x300_15_60(2)	0.4284	-31.95%	-15.97%	85.65%	5.45%	2.73%	0.4131	-34.38%	-17.19%	84.22%	3.69%	1.85%
300x300_15_60(4)	0.3520	-44.08%	-11.02%	86.67%	6.71%	1.68%	0.3038	-51.73%	-12.93%	85.34%	0.07%	1.27%
300x300_15_60(6)	0.2456	-60.98%	-10.16%	87.29%	7.48%	1.25%	0.2325	-63.07%	-10.51%	84.88%	4.50%	0.75%
300x300_15_60(12)	0.1476	-76.54%	-6.38%	89.09%	9.69%	0.81%	0.1294	-79.44%	-6.62%	86.68%	6.73%	0.56%
300x300_15_60(18)	0.1197	-80.98%	-4.50%	88.87%	9.41%	0.52%	0.0868	-86.21%	-4.79%	84.88%	4.51%	0.25%
300x300_15_60(24)	0.1151	-81.71%	-3.40%	88.84%	9.38%	0.39%	0.0534	-91.52%	-3.81%	85.14%	4.83%	0.20%

tions are increased or decreased, regarding the number of routers considered. Concluding that the deployment of relay nodes is a good way to optimise such networks.

As future extensions of this work, it would be interesting to include other fitness functions and to increase the size of the experimental instances used. Conducting real-world experiments and including features in the optimisation process from standard simulation tools, such as ns2 and ns3, are also future lines of research.

Acknowledgements The authors thank the anonymous referees for comments and suggestions which have led to an improved version of this paper. This work was funded by the Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness and the European Regional Development Fund, under the contract TIN2012-30685 (BIO project).

References

- Akyildiz I, Su W, Sankarasubramaniam Y, Cayirci E (2002) A survey on sensor networks. *IEEE Communications Magazine* 40:102–114
- Back T (1996) *Evolutionary Algorithms in Theory and Practice: Evolution Strategies, Evolutionary Programming, Genetic Algorithms*. Oxford University Press
- Cardei M, Du DZ (2005) Improving wireless sensor network lifetime through power aware organization. *Wireless Networks* 11:333–340
- Chang JH, Tassiulas L (2004) Maximum lifetime routing in wireless sensor networks. *IEEE/ACM Transactions on Networking* 12:609–619
- Cheng X, Narahari B, Simha R, Cheng M, Liu D (2003) Strong minimum energy topology in wireless sensor networks: Np-completeness and heuristics. *IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing* 2:248–256
- Cormen TH, Leiserson CE, Rivest RL, Stein C (2009) *Introduction to Algorithms* (Third Edition). The MIT Press

- Deb K, Pratap A, Agarwal S, Meyarivan T (2000) A fast elitist multi-objective genetic algorithm: Nsga-ii. *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation* 6:182–197
- Fonseca CM, Fleming PJ (1996) On the performance assessment and comparison of stochastic multiobjective optimizers. In: *Proceedings of PPNS IV*, pp 584–593
- Garey MR, Johnson DS (1979) *Computers and Intractability: A Guide to the Theory of NP-Completeness*. W. H. Freeman & Co.
- Geiger MJ (2008) Randomised variable neighbourhood search for multi objective optimisation. In: *Proceedings of EU/ME Workshop*, vol 0809.0271, pp 34–42
- Han X, Cao X, Lloyd EL, Shen CC (2010) Fault-tolerant relay node placement in heterogeneous wireless sensor networks. *IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing* 9:643–656
- Hays W, Winkler R (1970) *Statistics: probability, inference, and decision*. Holt, Rinehart and Winston
- Hou Y, Shi Y, Sherali H, Midkiff S (2005) On energy provisioning and relay node placement for wireless sensor networks. *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications* 4:2579–2590
- Hu XM, Zhang J, Yu Y, Chung HH, Li YL, Shi YH, Luo XN (2010) Hybrid genetic algorithm using a forward encoding scheme for lifetime maximization of wireless sensor networks. *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation* 14:766–781
- Jia J, Chen J, Chang G, Tan Z (2009a) Energy efficient coverage control in wireless sensor networks based on multi-objective genetic algorithm. *Computers and Mathematics with Applications* 57:1756–1766
- Jia J, Chen J, Chang G, Wen Y, Song J (2009b) Multi-objective optimization for coverage control in wireless sensor network with adjustable sensing radius. *Computers and Mathematics with Applications* 57:1767–1775
- Konstantinidis A, Yang K (2011) Multi-objective k-connected deployment and power assignment in wsns using a problem-specific constrained evolutionary algorithm based on decomposition. *Computer Communications* 34:83–98
- Konstantinidis A, Yang K, Zhang Q (2008) An evolutionary algorithm to a multi-objective deployment and power assignment problem in wireless sensor networks. In: *Proceedings of IEEE GLOBECOM*, pp 1–6
- Lanza-Gutierrez J, Gomez-Pulido J, Vega-Rodriguez M (2013a) A trajectory algorithm to solve the relay node placement problem in wireless sensor networks. In: *Theory and Practice of Natural Computing, Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, vol 8273, Springer Berlin Heidelberg, pp 145–156
- Lanza-Gutierrez JM, Gomez-Pulido JA (2011) Instance sets for optimization in wireless sensor networks. <http://arco.unex.es/wsnopt>
- Lanza-Gutierrez JM, Gomez-Pulido JA, Vega-Rodriguez MA, Sanchez-Perez JM (2012) Relay node positioning in wireless sensor networks by means of evolutionary techniques. In: *Autonomous and Intelligent Systems, Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, vol 7326, Springer Berlin / Heidelberg, pp 18–25
- Lanza-Gutierrez JM, Gomez-Pulido JA, Vega-Rodriguez MA, Sanchez-Perez JM (2013b) A parallel evolutionary approach to solve the relay node placement problem in wireless sensor networks. In: *Proceeding of GECCO*, pp 1157–1164
- Le Berre M, Hnaïen F, Snoussi H (2011) Multi-objective optimization in wireless sensors networks. In: *Proceedings of ICM*, vol 1, pp 1–4
- Lilliefors HW (1967) On the kolmogorov-smirnov test for normality with mean and variance unknown. *Journal of the American Statistical Association* 62:399–402
- Liu L, Hu B, Li L (2010) Energy conservation algorithms for maintaining coverage and connectivity in wireless sensor networks. *IET Communications* 4:786–800
- Lloyd EL, Xue G (2007) Relay node placement in wireless sensor networks. *IEEE Transactions on Computers* 56:134–138
- Mahboubi H, Moezzi K, Aghdam A, Sayrafian-Pour K, Marbukh V (2014) Distributed deployment algorithms for improved coverage in a network of wireless mobile sensors. *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics* 10:163–174
- Mann HB, Whitney DR (1947) On a test of whether one of two random variables is stochastically larger than the other. *Annals of Mathematical Statistics* 1:50–60
- Martins F, Carrano E, Wanner E, Takahashi R, Mateus G (2011) A hybrid multiobjective evolutionary approach for improving the performance of wireless sensor networks. *IEEE Sensors Journal* 11:545–554
- Mini S, Udgata S, Sabat S (2014) Sensor deployment and scheduling for target coverage problem in wireless sensor networks. *IEEE Sensors Journal* 14:636–644
- Misra S, Majd N, Huang H (2011) Constrained relay node placement in energy harvesting wireless sensor networks. In: *Proceedings of IEEE MASS 2011*, vol 1, pp 25–34
- Misra S, Majd NE, Huang H (2013) Approximation algorithms for constrained relay node placement in energy harvesting wireless sensor networks. *IEEE Transactions on Computers* 99:PrePrints
- Mukherjee JYB, Ghosal D (2008) Wireless sensor network survey. *Computer Networks* 52:2292–2330
- Nigam A, Agarwal YK (2014) Optimal relay node placement in delay constrained wireless sensor network design. *European Journal of Operational Research* 233:220–233
- Peiravi A, Mashhadi HR, Hamed Javadi S (2013) An optimal energy-efficient clustering method in wireless sensor networks using multi-objective genetic algorithm. *International Journal of Communication Systems* 26:114–126
- Perez A, Labrador M, Wightman P (2011) A multiobjective approach to the relay placement problem in wsns. In: *Proceedings of IEEE WCNC*, vol 1, pp 475–480
- ur Rehman A, Abbasi AZ, Islam N, Shaikh ZA (2014) A review of wireless sensors and networks: applications in agriculture. *Computer Standards and Interfaces* 36(2):263–270
- Sha K, Gehlot J, Greve R (2013) Multipath routing techniques in wireless sensor networks: A survey. *Wireless Personal Communications* 70:807–829
- Shapiro SS, Wilk MB (1965) An analysis of variance test for normality (complete samples). *Biometrika* 52:591–611
- Tang J, Hao B, Sen A (2006) Relay node placement in large scale wireless sensor networks. *Computer Communications* 29:490–501
- Wang B (2011) Coverage problems in sensor networks: A survey. *ACM Comput Surv* 43:32:1–32:53
- Wang Q, Xu K, Takahara G, Hassanein H (2007) Device placement for heterogeneous wireless sensor networks: Minimum cost with lifetime constraints. *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications* 6:2444–2453
- Xu K, Hassanein H, Takahara G, Wang Q (2010) Relay node deployment strategies in heterogeneous wireless sensor networks. *IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing* 9:145–159

- Ye W, Heidemann J, Estrin D (2002) An energy-efficient mac protocol for wireless sensor networks. In: Proceedings of INFOCOM, vol 3, pp 1567–1576
- Yoon Y, Kim YH (2013) An efficient genetic algorithm for maximum coverage deployment in wireless sensor networks. *IEEE Transactions on Cybernetics* 43:1473–1483
- Zhang H, Hou J (2005) Maintaining Sensing Coverage and Connectivity in Large Sensor Networks. *Ad Hoc & Sensor Wireless Networks* 1
- Zhao C, Chen P (2007) Particle swarm optimization for optimal deployment of relay nodes in hybrid sensor networks. In: Proceedings of IEEE CEC, vol 1, pp 3316–3320
- Zitzler E (1999) Evolutionary algorithms for multiobjective optimization: Methods and applications
- Zitzler E, Thiele L (1999) Multiobjective evolutionary algorithms: a comparative case study and the strength pareto approach. *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation* 3:257–271
- Zitzler E, Laumanns M, Thiele L (2001) Spea2: Improving the strength pareto evolutionary algorithm. Tech. rep., Computer Engineering and Networks Laboratory (TIK), ETH Zurich